

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Return Migration Infrastructures of the Netherlands

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Table of Contents

Summary.....	3
List of abbreviations	4
The GAPs Project	6
Acknowledgements	6
Funding acknowledgement.....	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1. Brief introduction of Return Migration Infrastructures in the Netherlands	7
1.2. Conceptualizing Return Migration Infrastructures	8
2. Methods.....	11
2.1 General methodological approach WP3	11
2.2 Data collection and methods for the Dutch case.....	11
3. A concise migration history of the Netherlands.....	13
3.1. Migration dynamics in the Netherlands	13
3.2 Social, economic and political conditions shaping migration.....	14
3.3. Return migration: some trends and figures	16
4. Return Migration Infrastructures in the Netherlands	19
4.1. A web of actors	19
4.2. Mapping MRI: Nodes, relations and materialities.....	21
5. Infrastructuring Assisted/Coerced Returns: DTenV Regievoorders	33
5.1. Infrastructuring Assisted Return: Positioning DTenV regievoorders and their Roles	33
5.2 Doings of DTenV regievoorders.....	37
5.3. Materialities & technologies	46
5.4. Relations: Synergies and frictions seen from the DTenV.....	55
5.5. Concluding notes	59
6. Infrastructuring Assisted Return?: Landelijke Vreemdelingen Voorziening (LVV).....	61
6.1. Infrastructuring Assisted Return: Positioning NGOs and their Roles in LVV	61
6.2. Doings.....	66
6.3. Materials & technologies	71
6.4. Relations.....	72
6.5. Concluding notes	76
7. Conclusion	77
References.....	79
Appendix 1: Overview of return statistics (Eurostat & DTenV).....	87

Appendix 2: The flowmap enlarged 88

Appendix 3: DTenV's Visualization of Return Migration Governance89

Appendix 4: Visualizing the LVV Programmes 90

Appendix 5. Visualizing the sharing of medical data 91

About the Authors92

Summary

Return migration has become a policy priority across the world, and especially in Europe. The GAPS project is a Horizon Europe project (2023-2026) that investigates the drivers of return policies and the potential disconnects between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes on the ground. It follows a de-centering approach to migration governance and seeks to move beyond a Euro-centric understanding of return policymaking. This report is part of Work Package 3 (WP3). WP3 is designed to study how return migration governance is **put into practice**, including how different actors collaborate or work against each other, and what discrepancies emerge and maintain to exist in their daily **operation** of return migration. In so doing, we work with the concept of Return Migration Infrastructures (RMI). RMIs consists of a multitude of state and non-state actors, the relations between these actors, the actual doings of these actors and the materialities/technologies that together put return migration governance into practice. These relations and interactions in governance arenas may actually create synergies, shared interests and coherence, but also frictions, boundaries, inconsistencies, clashes and dead ends. This report provides first an overview of the RMIs in the Netherlands by visualizing all relevant relations and processes in return migration governance. From there, and based on qualitative research techniques, this report zooms in on the ways RMIs operate on the ground with two in-depth case studies. The first case studies discusses the roles, doings, materialities/technologies and relations in the RMIs seen from the perspective of DTenV regievoorders. As part of the specialized governmental agency to materialize return migration – the DTenV [the Dutch Departure and Repatriation Service] – these case workers play a key coordinating role in the field. Subsequently, we de-centre the analysis of RMIs by focusing on the same dimensions (roles, doings, materialities/technologies and relations) from the perspective of NGOs that are involved in the pilot project called Landelijke Vreemdelingenvoorziening (LVV).

In combination, the discussion of the RMIs in its totality and the in-depth case studies foreground dynamic and complex realities shaping the Dutch RMIs. In other words, return migration governance should not be considered a linear and closed system. While fast-track forced removals do occur in the Netherlands, there are various feedback loops and escape routes in the system. Moreover, the forged relations across different levels of governance (local-national-European), and between governmental and non-governmental actors, create synergies, overlapping responsibilities as well as frictions. The complexity involved should not be misread as a policy dysfunction per se, as a large share of it is an inherent part of the migration governance architecture (e.g. the involvement of NGOs offering return assistance). The polycentric composition also allows for informal practices and information sharing across partners, making the landscape for the position of migrants more diffuse.

Keywords: Return migration governance, return migration infrastructures, coerced return migration, assisted return, materiality

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Dutch	English
AMIF		The Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund
AVIM	Afdeling Vreemdelingenpolitie, Identificatie en Mensenhandel	Immigration Police, Identification and Human Trafficking
AVR(R)	Vrijwillige Terugkeer (en Re-integratie) Ondersteuning	Assisted Voluntary Return (and Reintegration)
AZC	Asielzoekerscentrum	Asylum Location
COA	Centraal Orgaan opvang Asielzoekers	Central Agency for the Reception of Asylum Seekers
DIA	Directie Internationale Aangelegenheden (DT&V)	International Relations Office of DT&V
DJI	Dienst Justitiële Inrichtingen	Custodial Institutions Agency
DOVT	Directie Ondersteuning en Voorbereiden Terugkeer	Directorion Return Counselling and Preparation
DTenV	Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek	Departure and Repatriation Service
DTM	Directie Toezicht en Maatregelen	Supervision and Punitive Measures
DV&O	Dienst Vervoer en Ondersteuning	Transport and Support Service
ECSR	Europees Comité voor Sociale Rechten	European Committee on Social Rights
GL	Gezinslocatie	Family Location
HASA	Herhaalde Asielaanvraag	Repeated Asylum Claim
IOM		International Organization for Migration
IBIS	Integraal Bewoners Informatie System	Integral Residents Information System
IND	Immigratie- en Naturalisatiedienst	Immigration and Naturalisation Service
ISTV	Informatiesysteem Terugkeer en Vertrek	Information System Return and Departure
JRS		Joint Reintegration Services
KMar	Koninklijke Marechaussee	Royal Police

LKO	Lokaal Ketenoverleg	Local Chain Consultation
LSO	Lokaal Samenwerkingsoverleg	Local Collaboration Meeting
LVV	Landelijke Vreemdelingenvoorziening	National Alien Service / A shelter and return program, hosted in five cities in the Netherlands
MOB	Met Onbekende Bestemming	Destination Unknown
MRT		Multidisciplinary Review Team
PBL	Procesbeschikbaarheidslocatie	Location with the permanent obligation to be available
RAO	Regionaal Afstemmingsoverleg	Regional Coordination Body
REAN		Return and Emigration Assistance programme
RGOA	Regiegroep Ongedocumenteerde Amsterdam	Coordinating Group Undocumented People Amsterdam
RIAT		Reintegration Assistance Tool
RMI		Return Migration Infrastructure
RRC		Return and Reintegration Counselling
VBL	Vrijheidsbeperkende Locatie	Freedom Restricted Center
VOW	Vertrek Onbekend Waarheen	Independent Departure Without Supervision
VNG	Vereniging van Nederlandse Gemeenten	Association of Dutch Municipalities
VWN	Vluchtelingenwerk Nederland	National Refugee Council

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU’s return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

This country report of the Netherlands is part of Work Package 3 of the GAPS project. WP3 is designed to study how return migration governance is put into **practice**, including how different actors collaborate or work against each other, and what discrepancies emerge and maintain to exist in their daily **operation** of return migration, in Europe and beyond. Our study on Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs) focuses on the so-called ‘crucial meso-level’ (Faist 2021). The objective of WP3 is to better understand how the **relations and interactions** between actors, materials, and technologies together mediate /shape – i.e. facilitate *or* undermine – the ways return migration governance is actually happening on the ground. It thus starts from the idea that straightforward policy formations on paper, create messy realities on the ground through practices (Koinova 2024).

Before we present the conceptual framework of return migration infrastructures, it is relevant to demarcate our analytical focus for WP3 vis-à-vis the other work packages. Positioning the Return Migration Infrastructure as the **meso-level** implies that all that has to do with the macro-level of policy formation, law, international agreements, state agendas and diplomacy is outside our scope (this is covered by WP2, WP4 and WP5). Equally so, all micro-level analysis on migrant agency, their aspirations and experiences is out of our scope (this is mainly covered by WP7 and WP8). Henceforth, in its essence, WP3 focuses on the daily enmeshed operations of return migration governance that may involve a wide variety of actors (e.g. practitioners, frontline workers, NGOs, lawyers), relations, doings as well as materials and technologies. We thereby do not reproduce a simplistic binary of voluntary/forced returns, but start from the notion that return migration governance is characterized by a continuum of coercion instead (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou 2024; see also Kalir and Wissink 2016).

1.1. Brief introduction of Return Migration Infrastructures in the Netherlands

The Netherlands is considered to have a stringent post-arrival enforcement regime that is characterized by *a high interest* in enforcing returns as well as *a strong capacity* to do so (Leerkes and Van Houte 2020). This is reflected in the combination of a) policy mechanisms that reduce the space to manoeuvre for people without a right to stay (Ebrahim and Strik 2024; Van der Leun and Bouter 2015), b) governmental alignment of migration-related authorities (‘de vreemdelingenketen’), including a specialized governmental agency that is responsible for the governing of return processes, the Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek (DTenV), c) the existence of specialized migrant detention centers to materialize forced removals of migrants and to incentivize assisted returns from these detention space, and d) the incorporation of non-state actors in return counselling (e.g. Kox and Staring 2022; Kalir and Wissink 2016; Van Houte 2022). The latter concerns the well-established International Organization for Migration (IOM), smaller and pre-existing NGOs that have made use of, among others, DTenV subsidies to turn return assistance into one of their core tasks (e.g. Staring and Kox 2020) as well as relatively new NGOs that jumped into this field of return migration governance. As a result, and in longer-term comparison with other European countries (including among others

Norway, France, Germany, Italy and Sweden) the Netherlands have higher return rates (for both forced removals as well as assisted returns) (Leerkes and Van Houte 2020).¹

In line with the overall GAPS research objectives, this report primarily focuses on return migration governance to the countries of origin, and does not concentrate on Dublin claims or resettlement to third countries. Although Germany recently started to actively control its land borders, and despite a more right-wing turn in the Dutch political climate, we have found no evidence of push-backs from, or to, the Netherlands. In this report, we also do not pay attention to border refusals. Hence, we primarily focus on forced removal and assisted return of migrants without the right to stay in the Netherlands as the two operational forms of return migration governance for this country dossier. This report mainly captures the development until early October 2024, and excludes the migration related proposals by the newly installed government.

1.2. Conceptualizing Return Migration Infrastructures

States and supra-states rely on a multitude of actors to put return migration governance into practice. This, for example, concerns commercial security companies being involved in the pre-removal detention centers, flight operators that transport migrants (Walters 2018), NGOs that are offering assisted return programmes to to-be-returned migrants (e.g. Kalir and Wissink 2016; Marino et al. 2023), communities and local NGOs that are involved in reintegration processes in the countries of origin (e.g. Wanki et al. 2022; Marino et al. 2023) and, of course, powerful international organisations like the IOM (Bradley 2017; Maâ 2024). In addition, there are also multiple actors that negotiate or contest return operations initiated by states, which may apply to, among others, migrant advocacy groups (Moghaddari 2021), lawyers, local communities (e.g. Schapendonk 2023), employers and migrant groups (Nyers 2023; Kocher and Stuesse 2021). Furthermore, relations and interactions in governance arenas may actually create synergies, shared interests and coherence, but also frictions, boundaries, inconsistencies, clashes and dead ends (e.g. Godin et al. 2022; Vigneswaran and De Léon 2022; Marino et al. 2023).

To gain in-depth insights into the ways return migration governance is *put into practice* we put central the concept of **Return Migration Infrastructures**. Through this lens of migration infrastructures (e.g. Xiang and Lindquist 2014; Kleist and Bjarnesen 2019; Lin et al. 2017), we seek to contribute to the migration governance debate with an argument stressing complexity. In other words, we move away from the idea that return migration can be explained and understood by looking only at the way states design their policy and legal frameworks, or the way particular actors, such as street level bureaucrats, work with discretionary powers and autonomy (e.g. Kalir 2023). In other words, governance is put into practice through social and social-material relations.

Arguably, one of the most significant starting points for the infrastructural turn in migration studies is the intervention by Xiang and Lindquist in 2014. Their paper defines migration infrastructures as ‘the systematically interlinked technologies, institutions and actors that

¹ This comparative study compared the Netherlands with 11 other European countries, and for both assisted returns and forced removal the Dutch case showed a return rate of above 20%.

facilitate and condition mobility' (2014, p. S122). It is a productive lens to understand how migration processes are not only a question of migrant decisions or the outcome of an autonomous government agency. The infrastructural approach underlines that migrants do not only move by themselves, but their movements are constantly mediated by a wide variety of actors – some actors facilitate their movements while others control them (Xiang and Lindquist 2014). This **mediation** is crucial to understand the power-ridden character of migration and mobility across the globe (Lin et al. 2017), including its dynamic and at times contradictory processes at play. With regard to the latter, we question any systemic or structurally fixed connotation of infrastructures and we build in significant analytical space to the disconnects, frictions, discontinuities, and inconsistencies that may emerge.

In terms of operationalizing RMIs, the entire GAPS research consortium works along a continuum of coercion (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou 2024) that includes three prototypes of return.

1. **Assisted returns:** Assisted returns are defined as (1) departures of migrants from the host country, (2) who formally comply/consent with their departure (even though there is often pressure to do so), and (3) receive a level of logistical, financial, administrative and / or interpersonal support in the process.
2. **Forced removal:** Forced removals are defined as (1) the removal of migrants from a particular state after the arrival of the migrant in that state, (2) without migrant's consent, but (3) within the legal framework and procedures of the state. Except from the actual transporting outside the territory of a particular state, infrastructures of forced removal, may include, pre-removal detention, arrests, and escorting.
3. **Pushbacks:** Pushbacks are defined as states and supra-states practices of (1) moving migrants, who are at or near the border, away from their territories (2) by force and (3) before they officially enter that territory, which implies that they are obstructing access to the applicable legal and procedural frameworks of that territory.

This threefold distinction is rather a prototypical divide, as reality may involve many grey zones and overlaps in return practices (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou 2024).

With this continuum of coercion, we look at four main infrastructural dimension with the following questions:

1. **Actors and their roles.** What actors are involved in return migration governance, what are their roles and responsibilities?

This question focuses on the characteristics of actors involved, their roles, responsibilities and mandates through the eyes of the respondents mainly working from the street-level.

2. **Doings:** What do these actors do in the everyday practice and how do they facilitate *or* contest the implementation of return migration governance through their daily practices?

This dimension unpacks the daily reality of those actors working in the return migration infrastructure as a web of relations.

3. **Materials and technologies:** What materialities and technologies mediate return migration through the everyday doings of return migration governance?

The mediation of migration is certainly not only a human reality, but equally so a non-human reality of pre-removal detention centers, airplanes, specialized vans (e.g. Walters 2024). Additionally, surveillance techniques, software development and datafication are inherent components of return migration governance (e.g. Leurs 2023). This dimension pays explicit attention to these non-human elements in the RMI.

4. Relations between actors. How do different actors relate to each other? What synergies and frictions emerge in these relations?

By taking into consideration the first three dimensions, this question looks at the aggregate level of the RMI and evaluates how return migration governance is facilitated or contested in these relational spaces. Below we present the conceptual framework that is guiding the work of all research partners of WP3.

Figure 1. Operationalization of Return Migration Infrastructures. Source: GAPs consortium 2023

2. Methods

2.1 General methodological approach WP3

The WP3 research lasted from June 2023 to June 2024 and included two main tasks. First, creating an overview of RMIs in the case country by producing flow maps through desk research. Desk research included the study of reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, websites, etc. on the implementation of returns, from involved actors and/or observers, following the study of the legal framework on return migration (based on WP2). Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around i) the actors involved, ii) their doings, and iii) the materials and technologies used. Second, the WP3 research focused on the selection of a particular RMI type (assisted returns, forced removal, and pushbacks) as a case study. The research started from a specific “entry point” on the ground related to the everyday workings of the RMI selected. It included the implementation of 22 in-depth interviews in the Netherlands with in total 26 people involved at the meso-level of the everyday operation of the return procedure, that may both facilitate and contest return operations. All interviewees were provided an Information Letter and signed the Consent Form of participation in the research.

2.2 Data collection and methods for the Dutch case

To gain in-depth insights into the role of actors, the relations between actors, the actual doings of actors and the materialities and technologies they rely on, we have conducted desk research, held in-depth interviews and made use of ethnographic techniques such as observations. The in-depth interviews were held with the following actors:

- Five regiovoorders of Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek [Repatriation and Departure Service of the Dutch state] working from three different locations: a regular asylum location (AZC), a family centre (GL) and a migrant detention centre. In the report they are called DTenV regiovoorders.
- Four case managers of Centraal Orgaan opvang Asielzoekers/COA (The Central Agency for the Reception of Asylum Seekers), working from two different locations: a regular AZC and a family centre. In the report they are called COA case managers.
- Two representatives of the Immigratie- en Naturalisatiedienst (IND) (the Immigration and Naturalisation Service of the Dutch state) involved in the LVV programme. In the report they are called IND representatives.
- Four representatives of the International Organization for Migration (IOM), working from different locations: a regular AZC, a family locations, a migrant detention centre and Schiphol Airport. In the report they are called IOM officers.
- Four organisations with coordinating/central roles in the Landelijke Vreemdelingen Voorziening (LVV)². The NGOs are called NGO in LVV programme in this report.
- One LVV project leader from a municipality.

² The LVV has been a 5-years pilot programme that aimed to coordinate the accommodation facilities for migrants without the right to stay² in the Netherlands on a national level. NGOs, municipalities and state actors are involved.

-
- Four NGOs explicitly working on return counselling and providing return assistance.³ They are called NGO Return Assistance in this report.
 - One NGO providing legal support to migrants and one migrant rights activist.

Some interviews happened with two interlocutors at the same time, and some actors have been interviewed more than once. We also received written responses to our interview questions from Dienst Vervoer en Ondersteuning (DV&O), the transportation service of the Dutch Ministry of Security and Justice. When we refer to this document, we state *Interview DV&O*. Our attempt to connect to the Dutch Royal Police – Koninklijke Marrechaussee – did not lead to an actual interview.

In addition to the interviews, the Dutch research team has used observations during our visits to one regular AZC, one family location, one detention centre and two LVV locations. Observations have been reported during guided tours of particular practitioners, one meeting of governmental actors, as well as longer-term engagements with one LVV organization.

The interviews have been checked by the interviewees, and anonymized by us. In case we refer to interviews that might be traceable to concrete people or non-governmental organizations, we in general chose to not refer to a concrete location, and we might avoid mentioning the concrete interview. In an exceptional case, for instance when we discuss media coverage and public exposure, we do disclose the name of the non-state organizations involved. The state actors involved – DTenV, IND and COA – also participated in this research on the condition that they were able to read and fact-check this report before it is published. In addition, this report is reviewed by one external expert that is not part of the GAPS consortium as well as two experts of the GAPS consortium.

³ There are in total 6 NGOs working with this profile that receive funding from the DTenV. The DTenV budget to fund these NGOs reaches 3.6mln in total (NRC 2024a)

3. A concise migration history of the Netherlands

As an effect of intensified globalization, a colonial history and an open economy, The Netherlands can be considered a migration society or migration state (Adamson et al. 2024). This is not only characterized by various demographic impacts, but also by increasing dynamism or transience of incoming and outgoing mobility (Jennissen et al. 2023). This chapter only offers a brief historical sketch of Dutch migration dynamics over the past 25 years, highlighting the key phases of migration (Section 3.1), and outlining some of the main social, economic, and political conditions and incidents that have shaped Dutch (return) migration infrastructures up to the present day (Section 3.2). Finally, Section 3.3 will present trends and data that illustrate the current dynamics and infrastructures of return migration in the Netherlands.

3.1. Migration dynamics in the Netherlands

The past 25 years of Dutch immigration of Dutch migration history are central to this paragraph. However, it is important to take into account the migration tendencies of the decades before, as these were the breeding ground for subsequent phases of migration. In the '60's and '70's, immigration to the Netherlands was characterized by postcolonial migration (mainly from Suriname, the former Dutch Antilles and Indonesia) as well as the recruitment of large number of guestworkers, mainly from Morocco and Turkey.⁴ From this period, the Netherlands is in general considered to be an immigration country, with labour migration, family reunification, study migration and asylum as four important statistical categories. Yet, between 2000 and 2025 there have been subsequent years with a negative migration rate ('migratiesaldo')⁵ (from 2002 to 2007), meaning more people left the country as emigrants than entered the country as immigrants. In this period, labour migration from Eastern Europe became more significant, especially from Poland.

While family reunification and labour migration have traditionally been the most important migration patterns, violent conflicts in the 1990s also led to considerable asylum migration to the Netherlands. From 2000 to 2012, asylum migration to the Netherlands fluctuated, peaking at roughly 43,000 first applications in 1998-2000. This number dropped sharply following the stricter Aliens Act of 2001 (Van Meeteren et al., 2013) to considerably rise again in 2015 (Syrian war, Arab Spring, European reception crisis) and in the period 2022-2024 (after the Russian invasion of Ukraine) (see also Odé et al. 2023; Jennissens et al. 2023).

⁴ When the formal recruitment of labour ended in 1975, some guest workers returned to their countries of origin but the majority stayed permanently and brought over their families (Van Meeteren, 2013; Lucassen and Lucassen, 2015). Consequently, between 1976 and 2005, family formation and reunification of Turkish and Moroccan guest workers is an important migration pattern in the Netherlands (Jennissen et al., 2022; Lucassen and Lucassen, 2015).

⁵ The term migratiesaldo is the official statistical term used to count the sum of incoming migrants minus the number of emigrants. CBS counts only four subsequent years with a negative migration surplus (2004-2007). The corrected surplus rates, being based on the same data, takes into account administrative errors. Following these corrected numbers, there were six years with a negative migratiesaldo, starting in 2002 and ending in 2007.

3.2 Social, economic and political conditions shaping migration

Between the post-war years and 1980s, return migration governance, including forced removals, have only been marginally present in Dutch migration governance. In this period, there have been little societal controversy regarding unregistered workers and irregular residence. This changed gradually from the late 70s, with increased mediatized attention for undocumented people.

The Bijlmerramp of 1992, when a Boeing airplane crashed into a migrant neighbourhood in Amsterdam, can be considered an important tipping point in questions of irregularity in the Netherlands. The Netherlands was confronted with an ‘invisible population’ and official reports counting 40 deaths after the plane crash have been widely questioned as they might have missed many unregistered migrants. In the period that followed, some 2000 unregistered migrants reported themselves in the hope to be eligible for obtaining a residence permit as victim of the Bijlmerramp (Van Eijl 2012). From this period onwards, policies have been implemented that made irregular labour and residence much more difficult in the Netherlands, with the Koppelingswet [‘Linking Act’] of 1998 as the most notable example (see also Van der Leun and Bouter 2015; Ebrahim and Strik 2024; Van de Broek 2024). In addition, with the ‘notitie terugkeerbeleid’ [return migration policy note] of 1997, assisted and coerced returns became more prominent policy items (Van Houte 2022).⁶

In the early 2000s, the Netherlands faced a turbulent social and political landscape regarding migration and integration (Lucassen and Lucassen 2015). Despite the fact that Dutch migration and integration policies in the 1990s have often been referred to as ‘multiculturalist’, immigrant groups faced significant integration challenges, including higher unemployment rates and forms of criminalisation (Lucassen and Lucassen 2015; Van Meeteren 2013). Anti-immigration sentiments in Dutch public- and political discourse intensified. This ‘pessimist turn’ (Lucassen and Lucassen, 2015) is marked by the emerging popularity of Pim Fortuyn, a populist politician who, in the wake of the 9/11 attacks in 2001, explicitly propagated against immigration and the influence of the Islam. Fortuyn claimed that migrants, particularly Muslims, were threatening Western liberal values and Dutch culture (Berkhout et.al., 2015; Wekker 2016). In March 2002, Fortuyn gained political territory, launched as a candidate in the national elections, but was assassinated soon after. After Fortuyn’s death, and without its leader, his political party LPF became the second largest in the national elections a few weeks later (Van Meeteren et.al., 2013, Lucassen and Lucassen, 2015). Due to internal conflicts, the LPF did not exist longer than five years. However, anti-immigration sentiments resonated in the rise of Geert Wilders’ PVV that is part of the Dutch parliament since 2006.

These political changes characterise the atmosphere in which the Benefit Entitlement Act (1998), the Aliens Act 2000 (2001) and the Dutch no-fault policy (2005) became operational. Whereas the Aliens Act was designed by PvdA politician Job Cohen (Labour Party), his successor Rita Verdonk became the responsible “Minister van Vreemdelingenzaken⁷” (Immigration Affairs) to implement and monitor this Act. The employment of these new legislations and policies resulted in – among other things – more restrictive asylum

⁶ COA - Tjidljin 30 jaar COA | www.coa.nl, accessed on 31-10-2024

⁷ Vreemdelingenzaken literally translates as “Aliens Affairs”. The Dutch expression vreemdeling equals the French étranger, or German ‘Fremder’. The Ministry can be best considered the “Ministry of Immigration Affairs”.

procedures, the deprivation of basic care provisions and rights for irregular migrations as well as the foregrounding of return enforcements (see also Ebrahim and Strik, 2024). With Verdonk's return migration agenda, the Dutch government started in 2006 with the organization of a governmental agency with the specific task and authority to return unwelcome migrants: *de Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek* (The Return and Departure Service) – which is now a key actor in the Dutch RMI.⁸

The policy emphasis on forced return caused an intense public debate on terminology. In her period as minister, Rita Verdonk was accused of carrying out *deportaties*, and this term is loaded in the Dutch setting as it has usually been associated with the Holocaust. The return agenda of Minister Verdonk also led to some concrete legal and political controversy. For example, in 2003 the Dutch state faced a conviction of the European Court of Human Rights for the unlawful removal of a rejected asylum seeker to Somalia. In 2005, she misinformed the Parliament about the returns of Congolese citizens about the fact that personal information of these rejected asylum seekers was shared with Congolese authorities.⁹ In 2006, she announced to return homosexual Iranian nationals to Iran, a country that had given death penalties to homosexual men in 2005, leading to public rejections from civil society organisations.¹⁰

Some years later, the Dutch migration debate centered around the basic needs and further exclusion of undocumented migrants – which is known as the 'Bed, Bad, Brood' debate. While the Dutch government had the ambition to deprive the right to shelter for undocumented people, the European Committee on Social Rights (ECSR) had urged the Dutch government to meet the basic needs of undocumented migrants (by providing 'bed, bath and bread') (Baumgärtel and Oomen 2019).¹¹ In April 2015, the governing coalition agreed to implement the ECSR decision, providing reception facilities to irregular migrants *under the condition* of cooperation on their return. This led to a pilot of the 'LVV' – a shelter and return program, hosted in five different cities in the Netherlands – in which municipalities collaborate with Civil Society organisations and governmental parties to seek for sustainable solutions for irregular migrants residing in the Netherlands (see Chapter 4 and 6). It is relevant to mention that the LVV is a compromise between the national government and the Association of Dutch Municipalities (VNG) as basically all municipalities had to close their existing shelters, and in return the five selected cities received state funding to run the LVV programme.

In the same period, the so-called European refugee reception crisis of 2015 also had an impact on the Dutch migration landscape. With more asylum applications (+/- 43.000 first applications in 2015, compared to the 10.000-15.000 first applications in the previous years),¹² the Dutch authorities searched for temporary 'emergency solutions' to accommodate asylum seekers, such as large scale emergency locations consisting of tents, former prison buildings, sport halls and commercial holiday parks. Next to the sudden peak of asylum applications, the lack of capacity to manage the inflow of refugees is caused by financial cutbacks in the migration sector, leading to the downscaling of staff and accommodations in the period prior

⁸ Podcast series Vertrekpunt Nederland, episode one 'De Oprichting', accessed on 19-9-2024

⁹ Podcast series Vertrekpunt Nederland, episode one 'De Oprichting', accessed on 19-9-2024

¹⁰ [Verdonk stuurt Iraanse homo's weer terug - COC](#), accessed on 19-9-2024

¹¹ [Verschillende inzichten in bed-bad-broodkwestie \(nos.nl\)](#), accessed on 19-9-2024

¹² [Vluchtelingen in getallen 2023_V04.pdf](#), accessed on 31-10-2024

to ‘the crisis’.¹³ The 2015 reception situation and inflow of refugees resembled the situation of flexible reception infrastructures that emerged from the mid-1990s to accommodate refugees from the Balkan and elsewhere. In 2015, some 47.000 asylum people stayed in an asylum accommodation of some kind. In the following years 2016-2020, this number of people in asylum accommodations dropped considerably to 20.000-27.000 people. From 2020, a rather new development is that people who are accepted as refugees stay longer in asylum accommodations due to the fact that no living space outside asylum is found for them. In other words, the ‘doorstroom’ [flow through] of people in the asylum system stagnates, which automatically increases the population pressure of the national application centre in Ter Apel, a situation that still exists at the time of writing. The widely debated ‘spreidingswet’, legally obliging municipalities to provide accommodations to asylum seekers, was implemented in 2024. This was seen as an important policy response to this stagnation. The Russian invasion in Ukraine led to a new peak in terms of numbers of people seeking protection in the Netherlands, leading to another round of flexible reception infrastructures. The coming and going of new asylum accommodations in the last few years creates some turmoil among local population in different parts of the Netherlands.¹⁴

In November 2023, the PVV of Geert Wilders became the biggest party in the latest national elections and joined the government as a ruling party. The new cabinet announced "The strictest asylum admission regime and the most extensive package for controlling migration ever". Some of the first foreseen interventions of the new right with coalition is to discontinue the LVV programme as well as the ‘spreidingswet’ (Kabinet Schoof, 2024, p.1). In the meantime, local governments, including Amsterdam, Groningen, Utrecht and Nijmegen, already indicated they will run their own local accommodation programmes for undocumented people, showing the continued political frictions or ‘struggles’ (Van der Leun and Bouter 2015) regarding questions of irregularity and return.

3.3. Return migration: some trends and figures

In Appendix 1 we provide recent and official data derived from Eurostat and DTenV that have been presented by Ebrahim and Strik (2024). As noted by others (Oomkens and Kalir 2020), these numerical overviews should be treated with caution, as data are not consistent across data bases¹⁵ and miscounting may occur through bureaucratic practices (Wissink 2021). Moreover, in a reaction to this report, the DTenV stated that some individuals could be confronted with multiple departure procedures. Hence, it is important to see the statistics below as files or cases and not individual migrants.¹⁶

¹³ For instance, COA faced a reorganization in 2012. In this reorganization the total FTEs of the organization was reduced from 1480fte in 2011 to 1236 fte at the end of 2012, [COA - Tjdljn 30 jaar COA | www.coa.nl](https://www.coa.nl), accessed on 31-10-2024

¹⁴ See also [COA - Tjdljn 30 jaar COA | www.coa.nl](https://www.coa.nl), accessed on 31-10-2014.

¹⁵ See also Schapendonk (2024): [Decentering Return Migration Research: Are we on the same page? – GAPs](#)

¹⁶ In general, migrants who fall under the Dublin regulation stay within one procedure until the ultimate ‘transfer date’. A regular application [reguliere aanvraag] is not necessarily a reason for a case outflow. In other words, DTenV might decide to keep monitoring a migrant who attempts to obtain a regular status. However, in case a migrant is flown out of the caseload for a valid reason and re-appears at a later moment, a new return procedure is started.

In general, it is safe to state that the data reflect a significant decrease of returns in the years of the COVID-19 pandemic¹⁷, and returns are on the rise again from 2023. The table below shows more disaggregated data that derive from the DTenV. The numbers show how in absolute terms outflow with departure peaked in 2019 (17.150) and remained rather stable in the years thereafter (between 8610 and 11.160).

Considering the fact that datafication has become an inherent part of migration governance, and its justification (e.g Frowd 2024), it is telling that DTenV does not only monitor actual returns, but also count and present even more detailed data. This can be seen as a way to produce public ‘proof’ that they are doing good work. For instance, for the year 2023 the DTenV counted 19.990 return conversation, 15.390 return procedures. In the same year, there have been 5920 flights booked, and DTenV has requested 2020 travel documents [‘vervangende reisdocumenten’] (DTenV n.d.). Our interviews with DTenV regievoorders indicated that these numbers are extracted from the software system that does not only register statuses of return processes, but also monitor the performance of DTenV regievoorders (see also Section 5.3).¹⁸

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Total inflow of cases DTenV	22.360	14.560	13.840	12.620	17.670
Outflow of cases DTenV: with departure	17.150 (76,7% of inflow)	11.160 (76, 6% of tot. inflow)	9.330 (67,4% of tot. inflow)	8.610 (68,2% of tot. inflow)	10.690 (60,5% of tot. inflow)
Total proven departure (= assisted return + forced removal)	7.290 (42,5% of tot. Departure)	4.280 (38,4% of tot. Departure)	3.730 (40,0% of tot. Departure)	4.300 (50,0% of tot. Departure)	5.740 (53,7% of tot. Departure)
Assisted return from the Netherlands	4.510	2.630	2.100	2.450	3.380
Forced removal	2.780	1.650	1.630	1.850	2.360
To Dublin Memberstate	No published data	1.280	850	970	1.520
To country of origin	No published data	2.740	2.620	2.750	3.630
To another country	No published data	250	260	580	590

¹⁷ Several DTenV regievoorders we spoke to stated how the COVID pandemic impacted the efficiency of their work in negative terms. One regievoorder, for instance, mentioned “in corona times we have been completely sidelined”

¹⁸ In a reaction, the DTenV stated that the system indeed monitors the activities, but it cannot monitor the ‘qualitative dimension’ of their performance (i.e. do you properly and effectively organize your return conversations?). The latter is monitored in a different way.

Independent departure without supervision: destination unknown	9.860 (57,5% of tot. Departure)	6.880 (61,6% of tot. Departure)	5.600 (60,0% of tot. Departure)	4.310 (50,0% of tot. Departure)	4.950 (46,3% of tot. Departure)
Outflow DT&V: without departure	4.680 (20,9% of tot. Inflow)	3.640 (25,0% of tot. Inflow)	3.840 (27,7% of tot. Inflow)	4.800 (38,0% of tot. Inflow)	4.700 (26,6% of tot. Inflow)
<i>Permit granted</i>	1.600	580	800	1.140	860
<i>Regular application</i>	320	180	160	<i>No published data</i>	<i>No published data</i>
<i>Repeated asylum application</i>	2.150	2.340	2.290	2.640	2.780
<i>Other</i>	610	540	590	1.020	1.050

Table 1: Zooming in on DTeNV statistics of return migration. Sources:

<https://www.dienstterugkeerenvertrek.nl/over-dtv/cijfers> and [Stand van de uitvoering | Over DTenV | Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek](#)

4. Return Migration Infrastructures in the Netherlands

This Chapter seeks to map and visualize the Dutch RMI in its totality, from there a deeper analysis is provided in Chapter 5 and Chapter 6. As a starting point, it is relevant to emphasize that the Dutch return migration landscape consists of a continuum of practices and a variety of actors. It implies that, for this study, and unlike other GAPS WP3 country dossiers, we do not make a strong division between so-called assisted/voluntary returns on the one hand, and coerced returns/forced removals on the other, as the actors, doings and materials that are involved strongly overlap. In addition, the widespread academic criticism towards AVR programmes questioning the voluntariness of return migration decisions through these programmes also applies to the Dutch setting, as the threat of deportation is very often at the background of return counselling activities (e.g. Kalir 2017; Cleton and Schweitzer 2021; Cleton and Chauvin 2020).

4.1. A web of actors

Based on our interviews, we consider the Dutch RMIs in its totality as a web of manifold relations – or as one interlocutor has put it: it is a ‘busy landscape’. At the very heart of this infrastructure is the so-called Vreemdelingenketen [vreemdeling = alien / keten = chain]: the chain of governmental agencies that govern migration in the Netherlands under the responsibility of the Ministry of Security and Justice.¹⁹ The Vreemdelingenketen has an inner core “de kleine keten” [the small chain / or inner chain] and a wider web of partners. The “kleine keten” consists of the following actors:

- Immigratie- en Naturalisatiedienst (IND). The immigration authorities responsible for admission, including the assessment of asylum applications.
- Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek (DTenV): This is the executive governmental agency that puts the Dutch return policy in practice. It consists of several units (‘directies’), such as, International Relations (DIA), Supervision and Punitive Measures (Directie Toezicht en Maatregelen), Return Counselling and Preparation (Directie Ondersteuning en Voorbereiden Terugkeer)
- Centraal Orgaan Opvang Asielzoekers (COA): Responsible for the accommodation of asylum seekers.
- Afdeling Vreemdelingenpolitie, Identificatie en Mensenhandel (AVIM)²⁰. This is a law enforcement unit that is responsible for supervising the lawful residence of foreign nationals.

In the wider migration governance chain, most relevant governmental bodies include:

¹⁹ With the new government in 2024, this shifted recently to the Ministry of Asylum and Migration

²⁰ Translated in English as: Aliens, Identification, and Human Trafficking Unit Police or Immigration Police, Identification and Human Trafficking.

- Koninklijke Marrechaussee (KMar). This is the Royal Police responsible for, among others, border control as well as escorting to-be-returned migrants to the airport's gate or during the flight to the country of origin.
- National police: National law enforcement.
- Dienst Justitiële Inrichtingen (DJI): This is the Dutch Custodial Institutions Agency that is responsible for all kinds of detention centers, including migrant detention centers in Rotterdam and at Schiphol Airport.
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs: This ministry is important for the establishment of diplomatic relations.
- Dienst Vervoer & Ondersteuning (DV&O): This is the transportation service of the Ministry of Security and Justice. This agency arranges the transport of, among others, to-be-returned migrants to various places (e.g. from and to migrant detention centers, to and from courts, to and from family locations [gezinslocaties], or transfers from asylum locations to detention facilities).

To understand assisted and coerced return in the Netherlands, it is vital to note that the DTenV is since its development in 2006 and inception in 2007 the most crucial actor as they have an overarching monitoring role in return processes, performed by “*DTenV regievoerders*” [case workers]. These regievoerders combine their role as return counselors (i.e. having return conversations or “*terugkeergesprekken*” in Dutch) with a coordinating and monitoring role – and if needed a more directive role – vis-à-vis other actors in de Vreemdelingenketen. The latter is reflected in the so-called Lokale Ketenoeverleggen (LKO) at regular asylum accommodations (AZCs) in which the regievoerder discusses and decides upon return strategies for individual cases with relevant *ketenpartners* (partners in the migration governance chain working on return). Next to the DTenV, this LKO involves COA case managers, the IND and AVIM.²¹ However, for the location we visited, AVIM did not participate in LKOs as it had put its priorities elsewhere.

The interaction between DTenV regievoerders and migrants is, however, not isolated from many other relations and conversations, and here the RMI starts to become more complex. Civil society groups, NGOs, co-migrants, lawyers, the IOM, commercial actors, neighbours, and local municipalities may well be involved and influence the negotiation of returns (see also Eule et al. 2018; Cleton and Schweitzer 2021; Van der Leun and Bouter 2015). For instance, COA case managers also indicated they played a mediating role between various actors, and are an important contact person for people in asylum. Interestingly, next to the DTenV regievoerders, the COA case managers have conversations on returns with asylum seekers. In fact, they may confront the migrant very early in the process with a *what if they reject you scenario* (Interview COA Case managers 1-3). Likewise, Vluchtelingenwerk (the Dutch Refugee Council) indicated they have also conversations on return with migrants staying in AZC locations. Self-evidently, migrants, especially those in the asylum procedure, also often rely on lawyers who may legally challenge rejections of asylum applications or attempt in other ways to regularize a stay. Then there are a range of non-state actors active in the field of return counselling. The

²¹ On their website, DTenV indicates that LKO consists of DTenV, COA, the local police, and oftentimes the IND. They may also include other actors on invitation.

To understand the complexity of RMIs in the Netherlands, we created the above flowmap that starts from five pivotal sites from where assisted and/or coerced returns are put in practice. These pivotal sites are indicated as green round hubs and include: a regular asylum accommodations (AZC = asielzoekercentrum), a family centre (GL = gezinslocatie), the Vrijheidsbeperkende lokatie (VBL) in Ter Apel, a migrant detention centre, the national accommodation for irregular migrants (LVV: landelijke vreemdelingenvoorziening). We visited these hubs for our fieldwork practices, except from the VBL in Ter Apel.²² As one may immediately notice from the flowmap, there is a lot of connections between these sites and consequently the RMI we picture is not a closed linear system, but rather a dynamic circuit that includes circularity and feedback loops. This dynamism is to some extent also acknowledged by the DTenV as they put a roundabout in the middle of their visualization of return migration governance in the Netherlands (Appendix 3). We do not claim this flowmap is an all-inclusive overview, as it was impossible to visit all relevant locations and speak to all relevant actors. We also possibly miss some scenarios, routes, procedures and actors. Even with this touch of reductionism, the map contrasts the usual goal of images and flow maps, which is creating overview. In our case, it appeared to be impossible to provide a clearcut and uncontested overview of how return migration governance actually plays out on the ground. This is already an interesting finding in the first place.

From the five pivotal sites, the flowmap visualizes the **diversity of actors** (red = state authorities, purple = NGOs and the IOM offering return assistance, yellow = the national refugee council (VWN), shelter organisations and migrant support groups, grey = local government, dark yellow = EU return programmes, green = lawyers, blue = other actors, including airlines). We also indicate the **coordination platforms where different actors meet** (squares in light grey) as well as **the processual outflow of migrants (where migrants go or are sent to next)** (dotted lines). The dark grey flag-like shapes indicate the outcome of the processes involved. Please note this is not an overview of asylum procedures, but it concerns situations where migrants have not been granted the right to stay, due to rejected asylum applications or any other situation of irregularity (see Van Liempt, Schapendonk, Campos-Delgado 2023 for the discussion on ways to end up as irregular migrant).

4.2.1 Return scenarios from regular AZCs

To understand infrastructures of assisted and coerced returns from asylum spaces, we first need to briefly picture the asylum system of the Netherlands. The Dutch asylum system consists of different types of accommodations coordinated by COA. There are application centers, pre-process centers (prepol locaties), process centers, permanent regular asylum locations, temporary regular asylum locations, emergency locations (“noodopvanglocaties”)²³, “gemeentelijke opvang”²⁴ and locations for return. The most important entry point for asylum seekers is the application center in Ter Apel, with a formal capacity of 2000 people. The official

²²From this location, rejected asylum seekers ‘work on their return’ for a maximum period of 12 weeks (COA - Reception centres for return | www.coa.nl, 22-8-2024)

²³These are locations with lower standards in terms of quality of living, shelter conditions and privacy (COA - Noodopvang en tijdelijke gemeentelijke opvang | www.coa.nl, accessed on 28-8-2024)

²⁴ Formerly known as “crisisnoodopvang” (crisis emergency centers). Instead of COA, local municipalities are the main governing bodies in these cases.

policy aim is to keep asylum assessments short, yet in recent years the Dutch asylum system is characterized by arrearages, delays, stagnation and insufficient shelter capacities. It is nevertheless worth to outline the standard procedure starting with the application phase at Ter Apel. This first phase consists of among others a formal pre-registration (“voorregistratie”), an interrogation interview by AVIM, the taking of fingerprints and some medical examinations. After this application some preparation period follows that allows migrants and their lawyers to prepare for the general asylum procedure. This general asylum procedure takes place in a ‘procesopvanglocatie’ [POL], which may involve a relocation to a place outside Ter Apel. In a normal situation this general assessment phase would last for 6-9 days with a six months ‘decision period’ (beslistermijn), but the default situation at the time of writing is that asylum seekers wait for a year or more for the first response of the IND.²⁵ In this general assessment phase, the IND takes the first interview (aanmeldgehoor) and this involves an IND officer and a translator, but also IND officers of the Regional Information Center who check behind the scenes the accuracy of the asylum storyline through online maps and supports the IND interviewer with additional information.²⁶ Some time after this first interview, the IND communicates its intended decision to the migrant which may be one of the following outcomes: extended asylum procedure, acceptance or rejection. In case of an extended asylum procedure, a geographical transfer to a regular AZC or process center follows. When an asylum application is rejected at an early stage – the authorities try to return the person from that moment onwards. In that sense, besides being a first point of entry, the asylum location in Ter Apel is also an exit centre. Like the DTenV is present in most asylum locations, the agency is also active in Ter Apel with return counselling and removal activities. In case returns are practically feasible, return conversations may result in assisted return from Ter Apel. In case there is no cooperation from the rejected asylum seeker, DTenV may legally arrange custody (“inbewaringstelling”) and on this legal ground DV&O transports them to Rotterdam Detention Centre from where return and removal activities continue (this may include conversations on ‘assisted return’ again). In this way, infrastructures of entry and exit strongly overlap.

Usually, regular asylum accommodations (AZCs) only house asylum seekers whose asylum procedures have commenced. However, due to an ongoing migration management crisis, the pressure on the central location for asylum registration in Ter Apel is relatively high. This in combination with a housing crisis which stagnates the outflow of accepted ‘status holders’, makes that AZCs currently house people with very different legal situations, including acknowledged refugees waiting to move to a new home as well as people who are in the so-called prepol phase (the phase prior to the actual start of the asylum procedure) (Interview COA case managers 1-3). When asylum seekers receive a negative decision on their asylum claim, they are in general allowed to stay for a maximum of 28 days in the AZCs.²⁷ However, in particular situations, especially when it concerns a formal rejection of a repeated asylum claim (‘Herhaalde Asielaanvraag’; HASA), this maximum period of time that one is allowed to

²⁵ Some 10 years ago, the IND processed asylum applications with a number of weeks, see also DE WERELD IN TER APEL, AFL 1 (BNN/VARA 204).

²⁶ Members of the Regional Information Center of the IND may assist the IND case workers during the entire asylum procedure.

²⁷ Occasionally the DTenV asks COA for an extension of this 28 days in order to materialize a forced removal.

stay in the AZC is reduced to 0 days. When the maximum period has expired, asylum seekers lose their right to shelter and are removed from this particular location.

In regular asylum locations, the DTenV is present to promote, prioritize and govern returns. Next to their activities, various forms of return counselling happen by COA case managers and Vluchtelingenwerk. The IOM is also often present, but it recently closed their local branch at one of the AZCs we visited, implying that appointments need to be arranged by phone from this particular location. Other NGOs offering return assistance are not present on a permanent basis at AZCs, but have their advertisement materials distributed at AZCs and may spread information through presentations and site visits.

The governmental agencies of the Vreemdelingenketen collaboratively and strategically anticipate a negative decision by the IND through a particular governance platform – the so-called LKO: lokale ketenoverleggen (local chain consultations). In these regular meetings, information on individual cases are shared, exit strategies are discussed and negotiated, this will be further discussed in Chapter 5. These are the possible scenarios we identified and visualized in the flowmap from a regular asylum location:

- Assisted return: The asylum seeker opts for one of the assisted return programmes offered by DT&V, IOM, Frontex (EURP), or one of the NGOs present in the field [ARROW 1 RETURN COUNSELLING]. According to the interviewees at the regular AZC location, assisted returns are actually rather rare from an AZC location.
- Detention (= inbewaringstelling). DTenV regievoerder requests detention, which is legally formalized by the DTenV Uitvoerend Ambtenaar (executive legal servant). On the day of detention, DV&O and/or the police holds an order of entry, and enters the migrant's room at an unexpected moment (the migrant is deliberately left uninformed). The DV&O informs the Uitvoerend Ambtenaar about the wellbeing of the migrant and takes him to Rotterdam Detention center. Other actors present during this process include COA case manager, DV&O for enforcement and transport, a professional interpreter, and in case medical situations ask for it, medical support staff. Upon arrival at the detention center, the executive legal servant of DTenV has a hearing with the migrant (often accompanied by a lawyer and interpreter), monitors the legal procedures and formalizes the detention (this decision is sent to court for a legal check) [ARROW 2 TRANSFER (COERCED)].
- Transfer to VBL = freedom restricted center in Ter Apel. In case the authorities think there is a potential for an assisted return, but they need more time than 28 days (i.e. the maximum period that people have a right to stay in the asylum accommodation) to materialize this, people are sent to the VBL location. People are taken by DV&O and are sent to the VBL in Ter Apel from where DT&V works for another 12 weeks on assisted return [ARROW 3 TRANSFER].
- Transfer to family center: In case, families with children below the age of 18 whose asylum application is rejected do not opt for assisted return and cannot be returned through coercion, they are sent to one of the family locations. Here the DTenV and other actors continue to work on return strategies, both assisted return as well as forced removal [ARROW 4 TRANSFER].
- Transfer to closed family location: This concerns families with children below the age of 18 whose asylum application is rejected. In this case, the family does not opt for assisted return and the authorities do have concrete possibilities for a forced removal [ARROW 5 TRANSFER (COERCED)].

- Evacuation (“ontruiming”): It involves a situation in which the 28 days limit has been exceeded, while there is no prospect of an assisted return or forced removal, and the person refuses to leave his/her room. People are then removed from their rooms and put on the street by the local police. They leave the AZC independently. In terms of administration, these cases are closed with the indication ‘independent departure without supervision’ [Vertrek Zonder Toezicht], with the sub-category of ‘ending of accommodation service’ [Beëindiging Opvangvoorzining]. According to the interviewees, such evacuation is rather exceptional [ARROW 6 EVACUATION].
- Independent departure with destination unknown (“Zelfstandig vertrek zonder toezicht”).²⁸ Although it is not an official exit strategy of the authorities, this scenario occurs rather often from the regular AZC we visited. It concerns individual asylum seekers or families who leave unexpectedly and out of sight of the authorities. They may move onwards to a different country or live lives in irregularity in the Netherlands. It is likely that some of them end up at some point in time in LVV locations [ARROW 7 INDEPENDENT DEPARTURE]. For DTenV, these cases are administrated as ‘Departure With Destination Unknown’ [Vertrek Onbekend Waarheen VOW]. This is formerly known as the still often used term ‘Met Onbekende Bestemming Vertrokken’ (MOB).
- Scaling up: In case it is a highly complicated situation or disagreement, the LKO may decide to upscale the decision on a return strategy to a regional coordination body - Regionaal Afstemmingsoverleg (RAO). This body consists of senior DTenV officers, COA location managers and COA regional managers as well as senior staff from AVIM and the IND [ARROW 8 UPSCALING].

In Chapter 5, we delve deeper into the roles of actors, the relations between these actors and the materialities involved.

4.2.2 Return scenarios from family centers

The family centers are locations that house families with underaged children that have no formal right to stay in the Netherlands. Usually these families have spent considerable times in a regular AZC. Compared to the AZCs, the family centers are characterized by a more sober regime (including less financial support and an obligation for adults to report themselves during every working day). COA is the main governmental body that is responsible for the management of these locations.

Although the policy intention is that families leave the Netherlands as quickly as possible, the reality shows a situation whereby many families cannot return, do not cooperate with their returns, or whereby the authorities fail to meet the criteria for a return. It seems that mostly families who know that they are not easily deportable, for example because their country of origin does not cooperate on deportations, report themselves to such centers. Some other

²⁸ In our interviews, the most often used term was MOB “met onbekende bestemming vertrokken”. Some interviewees indicated that the latest administrative term is “Vetrek Onbekend Waarheen (VOW). In its documents, the DT&V prefers to write about “zelfstandig vertrek zonder toezicht”, emphasizing that the migrant is out of sight of the authorities.

families never report themselves to these family locations in order to not be subjected to the mandatory return conversations with DTenV.

The reality of a long stay of migrant families in these family locations has profound consequences for them, and especially for children staying there, as the Inspectorate of Education underlined recently:

“Family centers are locations for families who are out of asylum procedures (“uitgeprocedeerde gezinnen”). Rather than several weeks, many families stay in these locations for years. It is therefore of pivotal importance that children and youth residing on these locations can access education and that their security and continuous personal development are guaranteed” (Inspectie van het Onderwijs 2023, p. 4, translated by authors).²⁹

Two of the inspection’s main recommendations for the family centers are: prioritize the interest of the children and work with more realistic time frames (instead of hoped-for time frames from a policy perspective). In this regard, many families reside in these locations until the youngest child of the family turns 18 years old. From that moment onwards they lose their right to stay in these family centers. Families and their lawyers may submit a renewed asylum claim (HASA) during their stay in these particular centers and this has some administrative consequences. Although these families usually stay in the same location, they are administratively transferred (“omklappen”) from the more sober regime to the regular regime of the AZC (Interview DTenV regiovoerder 4-5). In these cases, the location of residence remains the same, while the regulations change for them. In terms of return migration, it means that DTenV cannot proceed with any return activities as long as a HASA (or any other application for a residence permit) is running.

In terms of return outcomes, we identified the following options from the family location:

- Families opt for assisted return programmes offered by IOM, EURP/DTenV or one of the NGOs present in the field [ARROW 9 RETURN COUNCELLING]. This is monitored by DTenV. Assisted return is possible when the family cooperates with their return, the necessary travel documents are available, and the country of origin readmits the people in question.
- Transfer to the ‘closed family location’: The authorities meet all the criteria for a forced removal and send the family to a so-called closed family location. This label of ‘closed family location’ is somewhat euphemistical as it is located within a detention facility. Moreover, authorities, including DTenV regiovoerders, do use the same terminology of arrests [“inbewaringstelling”], escorts and detention as in the case of detention facilities in Rotterdam.³⁰ The material difference is that the family detention spaces are less ‘cell-like’ and that the space includes a large green area.³¹ Families stay in these ‘gesloten gezinslocaties’ for a maximum period of two weeks. From this closed family

²⁹ Quote reads in Dutch as follows: “Gezinslocaties (glo) zijn asielzoekerscentra waar uitgeprocedeerde gezinnen verblijven. Gezinnen verblijven vaak geen weken maar jaren op deze locaties. Het is daarom van groot belang dat kinderen en jongeren die op een gezinslocatie verblijven, toegang hebben tot onderwijs en dat hun veiligheid en een ononderbroken ontwikkeling worden gewaarborgd.”

³⁰ See also [Vreemdelingenbewaring | Terugkeer vreemdelingen | Rijksoverheid.nl](#), accessed on 24-10-2024

³¹ See [Gesloten gezinsvoorziening \(ggv\) | Over DTenV | Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek](#), accessed on 28-10-2024

location, DTenV continues to work on return [ARROW 10 TRANSFER (COERCED)]. The administrative outcome might vary as both assisted returns [ARROW 10a] and forced removal [ARROW 10b] occur from this location.

- Independent departure with destination unknown [“Zelfstandig vertrek zonder toezicht”]. Although it is not an official exit strategy of the authorities, this is a common scenario at family centers too. It concerns families who leave unexpectedly and out of sight from the authorities. For the sake of readability of the flowmap, we also subsume cases of evacuations under this arrow³² [ARROW 11 INDEPENDENT DEPARTURE/evacuation]. Families may then move onwards to a different country or live in irregularity in the Netherlands. It is likely that some of them end up at some point in time in LVV locations [ARROW 14 INDEPENDENT MOVE].
- Scaling up: In case of a highly complicated situation or disagreement, the LKO may decide to upscale the decision to a regional coordination body - Regionaal Afstemmingsoverleg (RAO). This body consists of senior DT&V officers, COA location managers and COA regional managers as well as senior staff from AVIM and the IND [ARROW 12 UPSCALING].
- Regularisation: This occurs when there is in the end a positive decision from the IND on a renewed asylum application (HASA) or any other regularization procedure.³³ According to our interviewees, this is a common outcome after a long period of residence at a family location. It proves that repeated asylum applications or other regularization attempts can be successful.³⁴ Prior to the positive outcome of an asylum application, the process may involve a transfer to the application centre in Ter Apel, from where the asylum cycle for families start again (Inspectie van Onderwijs 2023) [ARROW 13 HASA].

4.2.3 Returns scenarios from detention centers

To actually forcibly remove a person from the Netherlands, the authorities need to meet four conditions: A. legal condition (the person can – according to the law – be returned), B. the to-be-returned person is actually present/available, C. the person is detained, D. the person has valid travel papers to be returned. The latter is often the bottleneck for DTenV in various locations. For the DTenV, the diplomatic work of the DIA department is of crucial importance here, as they seek to convince representatives of the presumed countries of origin to confirm identities and/or readmit the to-be-returned migrants.³⁵

In the Netherlands there are two migrant detention centers: in Rotterdam and at Schiphol airport. In addition, as discussed above, there is the specialized detention facility for families, which also keeps women³⁶ and unaccompanied minors on the basis of Article 59 of the Dutch

³² The DTenV regievoerder said on evacuations the following: In practice, it does not happen often, but in cases in which we failed to return the people after such a long time [when the youngest child of the family has turned 18 years old] it happens that families are evacuated. They are put on the streets.”

³³ There is a ‘buiten schuld’ procedure indicating that migrants are not to blame that returns have not been materialized, this may include medical reasons.

³⁴ The DTenV regievoorders we spoke at the family location estimated that regularization counted for roughly ¼ of the total outflow of cases.

³⁵ In 2023, the DTenV has asked state representatives some 2020 times to confirm a migrant identity. In roughly half of the cases, the DTenV received such confirmation (DTenV n.d.)

³⁶ According to official statistics, the majority of detained migrants are men (97%), see [Infographic Vreemdelingenbewaring 2024 | Publicatie | dji.nl](#), accessed on 24-8-2024.

Aliens Law.³⁷ Finally, in February 2024, the Dutch media reports about de facto detention facilities that are called ‘procesbeschikbaarheidslocaties’ (PBLs). PBLs are presented as a pilot and hence can be seen as an experimental infrastructure. They are fenced-off spaces in the Ter Apel location specifically targeting North African asylum seekers that are often considered to be little-chance applications [“kansarme aanvragen”] or seen as ‘nuisance asylum seekers’ [=overlastgevende asielzoekers] (NRC 2024c). This newspaper article outlines that there are no legal grounds for detention, and hence the authorities work with a so-called ‘beschikbaarheidsverplichting’ (obligation to report), which involves a coerced activity programme and the obligation to report oneself several times a day. As the by then State Secretary stated: “We give you so many coerced appointments so that you simply have to stay inside.”³⁸

The detention center we visited - the Rotterdam detention center – exists since 2010 and is located at Rotterdam/The Hague Airport. It has a department of the Koninklijke Marechaussee (Royal Police) nearby. The detention center has a total capacity of 320 rooms (with a maximum of 2 persons per room). The center consists of different sections with space for 60 people. This detention center holds only male adults. Most detainees are kept in ‘regular sections’, while those with extra medical needs are held in separate sections. There are hearing rooms on the section floors, but also separate hearing rooms on the ground floor. Detention occurs on the ground that the authorities have a prospect of forced removal. Following the EU Return Directive, the Netherlands can only legally detain migrants if no lesser coercive measures can be used. If a detention period exceeds six months, the DTenV needs to apply for extension (“een verlengingsbesluit”). This follows again the EU Return Directive providing the possibility of 12 months extensions in exceptional cases. Hence, the maximum period of migrant detention in the Netherlands is 18 months (Oomkens and Kalir 2020; Ebrahim and Strik 2024), but according to our interviewees it seldom happens that people are detained for this maximum period of time.³⁹ At the same time, some of our interviewees indicated that there are a number of migrants with a more circular pattern, going in- and out of detention centers, which makes the maximum period of detention questionable in case one takes a broader timeframe.

Actors present in this detention facility include, among others, DJI staff (the Dutch Custodial Institutions Agency), DTenV, IOM, AVIM, Vluchtelingenwerk, several medical staff, including psychologists. The offices of, among others DTenV, IOM, Vluchtelingenwerk, are located right above the detention spaces and are strictly separated by secured doors. Many of the staff working in these offices visit the detention spaces on a regular basis. This counts for DTenV and IOM staff involved in return conversations. The center is regularly visited by the migrant solidarity group Stichting LOS, and also lawyers stay often in contact with detained migrants through visits and they may advise migrants to legally challenge their detention. Consequently, it may happen that the legal grounds for detention changes, which creates some administrative work. For example, in detention migrants may actually apply for a residence

³⁷ This article basically prescribes that a person can be detained if s/he is considered a threat to public order (see also, accessed on 28-8-2024).

³⁸ “We geven je zoveel afspraken op een dag, dat je wel binnen *mot* blijven” (NRC 2024c)

³⁹ In 2023, the average period of migrant detention was 39 days according to the authorities (DJI 2024).

permit.⁴⁰ In these cases, the AVIM needs to visit the person to formally change the ground of his detention. During this application period (usually four weeks), the DTenV cannot proceed with any activity related to the coerced return.

Despite the fact that migrants are detained, and despite the pressure put on them through continuous conversations, coerced returns are not the only return outcome from this particular site. We came across the following scenarios:

- **Coerced return:** When migrants are not returning through the assisted return programmes, and DTenV meets all the criteria for a forced removal, coerced return is put in practice. DV&O brings the migrant to a particular entrance, known as the G-pier, at Schiphol, where he is handed over to KMar. The travel papers (passport or laissez-passer) is handed over to the airline. In case the ‘risk analysis’ of DTenV indicates there is a chance of resistant behaviour by the migrant, KMar escorts the deportee on the flight. The migrant may also be accompanied by staff of Medicare in case of health concerns [ARROW 15 TRANSFER (COERCED)]. At times, it happens that there is a last-minute Article 64 claim (delay of departure based on health situations) or a last-minute asylum claim is submitted to IND. To handle these cases quickly, and to make returns still possible despite these claims, IND has installed a Last Minute Aanvragen team at Schiphol Airport [Last Minute Processing Team].
- **Assisted return:** The DTenV and IOM offer voluntary/assisted return options within a context of migrant detention. Compared to other locations, the European EURP programme is more frequently used in detention. Only occasionally, DTenV regievoorders in the detention centers collaborate with NGOs offering return assistance. In case of assisted return, the migrant is brought by DV&O to Schiphol Airport, and presented to the IOM desk at Schiphol, and from there the migrant is presented to KMar who guides the migrant to the gate [ARROW 16 RETURN COUNCELLING]. In a context of detention, however, the administrative line between voluntary/coerced return is particularly blurry and may shift within a few days (see also Chapter 5 and 6). At the same time, this administrative divide of forced vs. voluntary return does have a real impact on the migrant, not only for the use of force by the authorities, but also because a return that is administrated as ‘forced’ limits the options for the migrants in terms of visa application profoundly in the near future.
- **Legal ground for detention is lifted:** In this case, all the attempts by the authorities to return a person failed or are reconsidered⁴¹ [ARROW 17A DETENTION LIFTED]. The person is then guided to the exit port of the detention facility and taken by a taxi to the central train station of Rotterdam.⁴² The migrant then is administratively considered to have independently departed with destination unknown [ARROW 14 INDEPENDENT MOVE]. Some decide to move outside the Netherlands, others live lives in irregularity. It is likely that a considerable number of them ends up in one of the LVV locations at some point in time. As stated above, some people end up in a cycle

⁴⁰ [Vreemdelingendetentie algemeen | Stichting LOS](#)

⁴¹ DTenV speaks of three scenarios here: The lack of prospect of a coerced return; rebalancing of different interests (“belangenafweging”) or less heavy measure (“toepassing lichter middel”), see [Infographic Vreemdelingenbewaring 2024 | Publicatie | dji.nl](#), accessed on 24-8-2024.

⁴² One of the demands of the municipality of Rotterdam is that people leaving the detention center do not “roam around” the area of the airport (Interview DTenV regievoerder 1)

of detention. One DTenV regievoerder indicated the latter “happens quite regularly”⁴³ and referred to cases of Nigerian, Moroccan and Algerian migrants.⁴⁴ However, legal grounds of detention might also lead to a right to asylum application. In these cases, the COA allocation office is contacted and the migrant is sent to an asylum accommodation [ARROW 17B DETENTION LIFTED].

4.2.4 Returns scenarios from Landelijke Vreemdelingenvoorziening (LVV)

The LVV has been a 5-years pilot programme that coordinated the accommodation facilities for migrants without the right to stay⁴⁵ in the Netherlands. The official aim of this programme was to realize an intensive collaboration between municipalities and state actors in creating a national network of supervision and shelter arrangements in order to find sustainable solutions for migrants without the right to stay in the country. The LVV programme can be seen as the outcome of the state’s wish to fundamentally reduce the capacity of migrant shelters in the Netherlands, as they are seen as “counterproductive in the formation of effective return policies” (Mack, Verbeek and Klaver 2020, p. 1), while at the same time living up to the obligation of not breaching the ERCS standards, as discussed above.

The LVV programme has been funded by Ministry of Justice and Security and the Association of Municipalities of the Netherlands (VNG). In the operational sense, the programme has been led by the so-called Programmabureau (of the Ministry of Justice and Security) and five cities have been selected as LVV pilot locations: Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Utrecht, Eindhoven and Groningen.⁴⁶ In these programmes, local municipalities have a main coordinating/chair role. In the LVV programme, NGOs and national governmental agencies collaborate to create sustainable solutions for people living in irregularity. These sustainable solutions include three options: assisted returns, onward migration and regularization. The pilot locations all share some important methods, including intake and registration, legal screening, coaching and future-oriented conversations (including return). The default maximum length of stay in this programme is set on 18 month for each migrant, but in Rotterdam this programme time is limited to six months only. Moreover, one respondent stated that the organization ‘did not work with a strict time frame, but the programme usually lasts for one and a half year’.

The LVV pilot project has been elaboratively reviewed (Mack, Verbeek and Klaver 2020; Mack et al 2022). According to these reviews, there have been 2065 people housed in LVV locations,

⁴³ Literal Dutch translation: “Dat komt toch wel regelmatig voor”

⁴⁴ This circularity is particularly visible in cases of intra-European removals, as one DTenV regievoerder stressed. “There are people, you constantly see again. These are people who are returned to Poland, for instance, who have apparently very little problems with being detained, and who make very little progress. Afte being detained in Poland, they take the first Flixbus to the Netherlands again. We then advise, make sure you are back on track again, before you return to the Netherlands. You may well come back, but make sure you have a proper job, a proper income, a proper address. That is not so self-evident for everybody.”

⁴⁵ In principle, the programme excludes migrants with a heavy entry ban of at least 10 years, those migrants who have been officially declared undesirable (“ongewenst verklaarde vreemdeling”), Dublin-claimants, and EU-citizens (see also Mack, Verbeek and Klaver 2020; Regiegroep Ongedocumenteerde Amsterdam 2023). An additional criterion is that migrants should have a connection with the city or region of the LVV.

⁴⁶ For more information on the exact LVV governance structure see Regioplan 2020 (p. 27)

of which 75% were male (Mack et al., 2022).⁴⁷ Some 1258 people have left the programme. Of this group of migrants, 60% had either found a sustainable solution (e.g. regularization or return migration) or semi-sustainable solution (e.g. re-submitting asylum claims). For roughly 40% of people that have left the programme, no solution has been found. More recent figures are discussed below.

Despite the national coordination and the commonalities, the LVV locations have not formed a homogenous space. For each location, sub-objectives have been added by local municipalities and/or NGOs, and also the local constellation of actors vary across the cities. In Rotterdam and Groningen, for example, the local government takes a central coordinating role, while the same role is fulfilled in Amsterdam by an NGO. Furthermore, the particular histories of NGOs, their priorities, admission criteria as well as the local political environments they operate in differ considerably across these places. For instance, in Eindhoven the LVV location maintained the character of a Bed, Bad Brood location, implying that even people that do not meet the official LVV criteria can find shelter there. This is made possible by the extra funding provided by the municipality (see also de Haan 2024). Moreover, in different cities, the LVV programme has different capacities, ranging from 360 places (for LVV Amsterdam) to 45 places (for LVV Rotterdam)⁴⁸ (Mack et al. 2022) and occupancy rates vary considerably as well (+/- 90% for Amsterdam and +/- 27% for Rotterdam) (ibid.). In other words, despite the policy attempt to arrange a national shelter programme, the local articulations of this programme create considerable variations regarding fundamental elements of this programme.

The new government in the Netherlands, with the PVV Minister Faber, declared soon after its installment to discontinue the LVV programme from 2025. However, four of the five city administrations that are part of the LVV stated to continue financing local programmes to shelter undocumented migrants in some way, which indicates how migration governance is a contested field in the Netherlands. While we provide a detailed LVV case study in Chapter 6, we complete this mapping exercise by outlining the following outcomes of the LVV:

- Assisted return. After migrant's registration, LVV programmes decide in the LSO upon the trajectory to be followed. Return counselling is one of these trajectories. In these cases, the migrant is connected to a case manager from a NGO offering return assistance, such as Vluchtelingenwerk MOH, Stichting Ros or Goedwerk Foundation. In case, a migrant actually returns through these NGOs, this is administrated as assisted return within the LVV programmes. According to the latest numbers (August 2024), in total 208 out of the 2889 people that have been registered in the LVV programme have returned to their countries of origin (Ministerie van Veiligheid en Justitie n.d.) [ARROW 18 RETURN COUNSELLING].
- Independent departure. Migrants may decide to leave LVV programmes, or the programme is stopped. The migrant may then continue to live in the Netherlands

⁴⁷ Overview number of participants per location: Amsterdam (757 individuals), followed by Eindhoven (486 individuals), Utrecht (427 individuals), Rotterdam (241 individuals) Groningen (154 individuals) (Mack et al. 2022)

⁴⁸ From January 2024, the capacity in Rotterdam has been downsized from 117 to 45 beds.

irregularly, or leave the Netherlands independently.⁴⁹ About 800 trajectories in the LVV have not led to a so-called ‘sustainable solution’[ARROW 19: INDEPENDENT DEPARTURE (INCLUDING ONWARD MIGRATION)].

- Regularisation: Next to a legal screening, the LVV programmes offer legal counselling in cases where legal space to manoeuvre exist. According to the LVV monitor of August 2024, 370 people have been regularized by a repeated asylum application (HASA), and 75 people have been regularized for health-related reasons (Ministerie van Veiligheid en Justitie n.d.) [ARROW 20 REGULARISATION].
- Pre-removal detention ARROW 21: Pre-removal detention through the LVV programme is exceptional. This has only happened from the LVV location in Groningen (22x) and Rotterdam (4x) in the evaluated period (Mack et al. 2022)⁵⁰ [ARROW 21 TRANSFER COERCED]. Two of the respondents we interviewed stated that their organization only started with the LVV programme on the condition that forced removals would not be materialized from their locations. In their view, it would profoundly hamper the trust relationship with migrants that is necessary to make the programme work in the first place.
- Scaling up: If there is no agreement found in the LSO meeting for a particular case, the LSO transfers the case one level up: the Multidisciplinary Review Team (MRT). This team consists of state and non-actors who have not been involved in this particular case before [ARROW 22 UPSCALING].

With the returns seen from the LVV, we have completed the mapping exercise (see Figure 1 and Appendix 1 for an enlarged version). In the following two chapters, we provide two case studies by which we delve deeper into the migration infrastructure of assisted/coerced return. Following our conceptual model, we unpack the roles of actors, the doings of actors the materiality and technology involved and the relations between the actors. We first start with a case study focusing on DTenV regievoorders working on assisted returns. To de-center assisted returns, we then move into the daily realities of LVV programmes from the perspectives of NGOs (Chapter 6).

⁴⁹ As these movements happen outside the sight of administrative bodies, they are not administrated as ‘onward migration’ in the framework of LVV programmes. The LVV monitor counted only 12 persons who moved onwards with the help of the LVV programme.

⁵⁰ In addition, the LVV monitor of August 2024 counts 10 cases of people that have been returned from a detention center.

5. Infrastructuring Assisted/Coerced Returns: DTenV Regievoorders

In Chapter 4 we mapped the totality of the RMIs in the Netherlands. This map indicates a blurred line between assisted returns and forced removals and emphasized non-linear dynamics (circulations, interruptions, transitions), and in so doing, it complements the roundabout logics of the return process as it is pictured by the DTenV (see Appendix 3). We now zoom in on the RMIs from the perspective of DTenV regievoorders working from different locations: regular asylum seeker centres, family locations and one of the detention centers. We do not claim this chapter provides an exhaustive overview of all the relevant practices and relations in the field, it does however unpack some of the most important mechanisms of the RMIs we study.

5.1. Infrastructuring Assisted Return: Positioning DTenV regievoorders and their Roles

DTenV Regievoorders are responsible for the ‘coordination and direction’ of return processes of migrants.⁵¹ Basically every to-be-returned migrant known by the authorities is monitored by a DTenV regievoorder. Their main role is to have personal return conversations with to-be-returned migrants and to coordinate return processes with other ‘ketenpartners’. Regievoorders are asked ‘to take initiative’ in these processes and, if necessary, to find ‘creative solutions’ (within the framework of the law). Their professional role is characterized by autonomy, responsibility and a context of coercion [“gedwongen kader”], as the migrants they work with are present because they are obliged to do so (DTenV 2019, pp.5-7). However, as particularly shown in the work of Cleton and Chauvin (2020), DTenV regievoorders often foreground agency and degrees of freedom in their conversations with migrants in order to promote the assisted return option. In this context, DTenV regievoorders are trained on their cultural competences, as better and wider set of cultural sensitivities might enhance the efficiency of return infrastructures (see also Khosravi 2009).

When asked to describe their role, DTenV regievoorders responded in rather similar ways by referring to “being a connector”, “being the spider in the web” or as the person who is “arranging everything on the background”. While there is a strong connection, and some overlap, with the work of COA case managers (working at different asylum locations, but not in detention as in detention centers migrants are connected to a DJI case manager known as “medewerker vreemdelingenzaken”), the interviews show also some clear differences (see Table 2 below).

⁵¹ Regievoering can be best translated as directing (like a film director coordinates the making of a film). In some of the DTenV documents, reference is made to the terminology of ‘regisseur’ (film director) (DTenV 2019)

Formulations used by DTenV regievoorders to explain their role in the RMI	Formulations used by COA case managers to explain their role in the RMI
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spider in the web • Arranging everything on the background • Coordinating role with 'ketenpartners' • Having return conversations / being confrontational • You are planning constantly (prioritizing/postponing) • Role to inform migrants, particularly on return procedures • Administrative roles • Generating departures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust person for asylum seekers during different phases (intake, procedure, return) • Role to inform asylum seekers about their procedures • Holistic view on the situation of asylum seekers • Case manager in terms of housing, family issues, school, health, etc. • Having return conversations in an early stage (what if you receive a negative decision....?)

Table 2: Summary of the different roles as formulated by the research participants

Coordination, monitoring and putting returns actually in motion are the most important roles of DTenV regievoorders. And this creates a rather powerful position, as one interviewee indicated:

“I can send people to embassies, I can transfer people to a different AZC. In this regard, I do have quite some power. Yes, and you try to coordinate this as best as you can with ketenpartners to find the right decision” [DTenV regievoerder3, April 2024].

However, in different locations, the role of DTenV regievoorders slightly varied, from having a strong **coordinating role** in the regular asylum location and family location (as the chair of the Lokale Ketenoverleggen (LKO = local chain consultations with other state agencies) to having a more **monitoring role** in the LVV locations in the Lokale Samenwerkingsoverleggen (LSOs = local collaboration meetings with state agencies as well as shelter organisations and NGOs offering return counselling). In LKO meetings, information and impressions regarding particular cases are shared with other governmental actors in order to decide upon the return strategy. Basically, in these meetings DTenV is looking for consensus across the governmental actors (usually COA, IND, AVIM) to decide upon the existing options: assisted return, forced removal, transfer to VBL or family location, evacuation. Although the consensus-driven approach was confirmed by COA case managers, some of them also indicated that DTenV may put considerable pressure on other LKO members [Interview COA case manager 2] (see also section 5.4).

DTenV's monitoring role also unfolds through the subsidies they offer to the various NGOs working in the return landscape (see also Kalir and Wissink 2016).⁵² NGOs report back their progresses and need to justify their spendings. For the NGOs in the LVV programme, the DTenV subsidies work from the idea of an “inspanningsverplichting” [literally translated as the obligation to make a real effort], so they are not financed per case. Yet, the direct financial

⁵² This monitoring role went further than only financial and practical justifications, as also some of our interview requests were approved first by the DTenV.

relations create some power imbalances and conditionalities in collaborative settings (see also Chapter 6).

5.1.1 The DTenV method

In terms of case-load, regievoorders stressed the wide variety of cases, which adds to the complexity of their work. Some cases (especially Dublin cases) were referred to as ‘lopende bandwerk’, referring to the standardized labour of an assembly line, while other cases are considered to be super complex and require tailor made approaches. For our interviewees, case-load per regievoerder varied from 30 to 60 cases per person.

One of the common starting points is that DTenV regievoorders aim to build a rather particular trust relation with the migrant (see also Cleton and Schweitzer 2023), which one interviewee tellingly described as a “zakelijke vertrouwensband”⁵³ (DTenV regievoerder 1). The particularity of this relationship was further explained by DTenV regievoerder 3 by saying:

I describe my role as informing people, to tell them how their situation looks like, and I do this with the right tone, so there is no space for chit-chats.⁵⁴ No, people HAVE TO know when they receive a negative decision of the authorities.

Through this particular relation some level of trust is folded with directness and direction, and from this relation DTenV regievoorders engage with, and actively massage, the aspirations of migrants (e.g. Cleton and Schweitzer 2021; see also DtenV 2019). Soft approaches, such as stressing people’s brighter futures in the process, are often alternated with more stringent and directive conversations. DTenV regievoorders play a double role in the conversations with migrants, as they may foreground ‘voluntary’ or ‘assisted returns’, but they are also in charge of initiating forced removals when migrants refuse to opt for the former (see Cleton 2022). In that sense, it is crucial to note that in all conversations that occur in the context of coercion [‘gedwongen kader’] the possibility of a forced removal is always present on the background. Consequently, coercion and confrontation is often emphasized by the DTenV regievoorders we interviewed as inherent part of their conversations and relationship with migrants. Our interviewees used expressions like “raw conversations”. Others stressed their role of activating migrants as people who have stayed in asylum systems for too long “fall asleep .. and are not doing anything and often face depression” (DTenV regievoerder 4). The latter counts for regular asylum centers, but was particularly visible in the family location, as people regularly stay for longer periods of time.

While assisted return is regarded as still the preferred option in detention settings, the people we spoke to articulated the thin line between assisted return and forced removal in this context, as DTenV regievoerder 2 tellingly describes from a context of detention:

So, let us say, we have a travel document. Then it is a matter of booking the flight, and you go out [“het is boeken en wegwezen”]. If this is not the case, then we have to take a closer look. How is the physical and mental health? Nothing wrong, but that is rather rare these days, then OK, it is a matter of booking the flight, and you go out. Ah, you

⁵³ The word “zakelijk” translates as a “commercial relation”, which carries a connotation of coldness, pragmatism and straightforwardness in the Dutch expression.

⁵⁴ Literal Dutch expression of chit-chats, as used by the interlocutor: “ik wil geen koetjes en kalfjes naar voren halen”

would like to collaborate on your return? Great! We can order a DV&O transport, and they bring you to Schiphol. Ah, you don't want to collaborate on your return? OK, well then there is the extra securitized transport by Kmar, and they put you on the plane, and you are out.

In this synopsis – which is evidently a reductionist representation⁵⁵ – the line between assisted return and forced removal is reflected in the emphasis on coercion and the lack of alternatives [“het is boeken en wegwezen”] as well as in the different level of materialized securitization of the DV&O transport.⁵⁶ In this respect, some scholars underline that assisted return migration programmes are actually instruments to incentivize forced removals (e.g. Webber 2011; Walters 2018; Maâ 2023). With DTenV regievoorders, we discussed this thin line, and asked for their perspectives. Some stated how *forced removal* can actually consist of a very *easy and smooth* process without the use of force and without the presence of escorts in the airplane. Others referred to how assisted returns are often de facto forced returns as no other options than returning are presented to migrants. In other words, practices and categories of return blur and overlap rather easily, as this part of a conversation further illustrates:

Interviewer: When I look at the DTenV terminology, on their website, I don't see any more the terminology of forced versus voluntary returns. Then it is more the question are you assisted or forced.

These are nice terms yes [with some irony]

Interviewer: But they mean the same?

Yes

Interviewer: Then I think we are on the same page.

Marmelade is marmalade, whatever label you put on the jar⁵⁷

This quote illustrates a particular indifference regarding the administrative labelling involved in a detention setting. In the view of this regievoorder, the setting of detention would make any attempt to frame it as a non-forced move rather dubious. In this framework, it is worth noting that the DTenV stopped to use the voluntary return terminology and switched to ‘assisted return’ as the default term.

Navigating and working with the thin line between forced or assisted return is not only a daily practice for DTenV regievoorders. At times, NGOs offering return assistance find themselves in a similar situation. In some occasions, these NGOs contact DTenV for their assistance which creates blurry lines too, as NGO Return Assistance 2 outlined:

There are cases in which nothing really works, and then, in the end, although you don't want to, you knock on DTenV's door. You don't want that because people do get a different label then. There is more force. It is maybe not forced, but you are assisted by

⁵⁵ As a response to this reductionist representation of a departure procedure, the DTenV stated the following: “During the departure procedure the case worker monitors continuously the following aspects: poignancy, no-fault procedures [buiten schuld], art. 64 of the aliens act [health related] – human trafficking. The DTenV is particularly monitored by the health inspection on the extent to which health is properly monitored.

⁵⁶ One IOM officer put the limited space of decision making for migrants in a telling way: “The people I meet, they only have a few options, but they have options” (Interview IOM officer 2)

⁵⁷ “Jam is jam, wat voor etiket je er ook opplakt”

the DTenV. So the difference is, when you travel with us through IOM, it is a smooth process, but when you travel with DTenV then you are connected to the Marrechaussee, which creates a very different process. Not so nice [NGO Return Assistance 2].

Coercion is not only put on the shoulder of migrants, but from their daily realities in the detention center coercion is also put on the shoulder of DTenV regievoorders. One respondent emphasized:

We *have to* work on return. That is not a choice, it is the law. A mandate directly coming from the law. (DTenV regievoerder 2, April 2024)

This coercive element on their shoulder is articulated in the setting of detention, as DTenV regievoerder 1 stressed:

Our aim is to keep the period of detention as short as possible ...A person should stay in detention as short as possible, it is our ultimate measure ... the heaviest measure we have in our migration law, so we *have to* monitor the detention process. You simply *cannot* drop a stitch (DTenV regievoerder 1)

Interestingly, the former interview fragment stressing the law and DTenV's mandate indicates how street level workers 'hide behind the law' to justify their practices, as also underlined by the critical work of Barak Kalir (2023) approaching the DTenV workers' reality through Arendt's lens of banality of evil. The second fragment, however, articulates the DTenV's legal duty to materialize and monitor the legal limits to migrant detention. From these interviews, we state that these realities can be considered two sides of the same coin. Keeping the period of detention as short as possible is another way of saying that forced returns should be realized as efficient as possible.

5.2 Doings of DTenV regievoorders

To make sense out of the daily practices of DTenV regievoorders, we distinguish three main doings: **strategizing work**, **relational work** within and between organisations and **administrative work**. To start with the first, DTenV regievoorders are constantly navigating the possible options to return people who have no right to stay in the Netherlands. Their work basically starts with a return order of the IND, which concerns mostly rejected asylum seekers and declined applications for residence permits. With the blurry line of assisted/forced return in mind, one central element of regievoorders' daily strategizing work is anticipation, and this start from the moment they face a new case. How much willingness has the migrant expressed in relation to return? How much resistance can we expect? What kinds of legal means did the migrant use in the past, and what else is there to expect? What is the risk of an unexpected departure? Where is the pain for the person in question? In this anticipation, the DTenV regievoorders is not only interested in legal scenarios, but also, and very much so, in behavioral aspects of the migrants in question. Based on this anticipation, DTenV regievoorders create strategies, use different instruments, and also think ahead of the next steps. This is tellingly described by DTenV regievoerder 3:

Usually, people have a term of departure of 28 days after a reject. But for me, it is the most important to get an impression about them before this term starts. Are they likely to cooperate on their return? Usually, you know their files, and you know whether people are cooperating or not.

...

When there is a court hearing, you in a way already know what you have to do in these 28 days. Sometimes you can start planning the flight, but at times people might be more resistant, and then I may decide to have another conversation [on their return].

The strategizing element of their daily practices often depend on other actors, also beyond state authorities (see also Cleton and Schweizer (2021) on how case workers express their frustration regarding these dependencies). Especially the absence of travel documents is a major blockade for DTenV regievoorders. Hence, their strategizing activities often also involve investigations (in relation to identities). They may check former police reports, or trace documents that were found at an early stage of the asylum application. Or through their colleagues at DIA – the DTenV department working on foreign affairs and diplomacy – they may arrange presentations of migrants to the representatives of particular states the DTenV thinks the migrant originates from. Confirming nationalities is a crucial step to obtain the necessary travel papers. From the perspective of DTenV regievoorders, this requires diplomacy, and often, patience (see also Leerkes and Van Houte 2020). DIA is therefore considered to be a crucial department for daily operations of regievoorders.

A shared characteristic of regievoorders' work is that realities and opportunities may shift rapidly. New information (and especially the reception of laissez passers or other travel documents) requires a new range of actions. We often heard the example of how re-arranged diplomatic relations with Morocco made assisted/forced return to this North African country possible after years of reluctance from the Moroccan authorities to readmit irregular migrants. Consequently, the number of Moroccan nationals in detention has risen considerably in the last years (e.g Interview DTenV regievoerder 1 and DTenV regievoerder 5). Some time ago, a group of high delegates of the Moroccan state visited the Detention Center in Rotterdam and from then on, the Moroccan authorities provided more laissez-passers to facilitate the returns from detention. This is also reflected in a public message of the DTenV that announced the annual report of 2023. They stated the following:

For DTenV, 2023 was a year with good results. More people demonstrably left the Netherlands [“zijn aantoonbaar vertrokken”], a total of 5740. That is 1370 more than the year before. This result is partly a consequence of the improved return cooperation with Morocco and the efforts in the context of the remigration policy. We at DTenV are satisfied with the results.⁵⁸

Apparently, this is indeed the ‘geopolitical momentum’ to materialize forced removals to Morocco.

However, new realities are not always in favour of regievoorders as new counter steps can be made by migrants and their lawyers, making previous steps of regievoorders redundant or ineffective. In other words, strategizing work of regievoorders is based on constantly shifting grounds. What's more, strategizing work is not a solitary act of DTenV staff, but can be

⁵⁸ Original text: “Voor DTenV was 2023 een jaar met goede resultaten. Er vertrokken meer personen aantoonbaar uit Nederland, in totaal 5.740. Dat zijn er 1.370 meer dan het jaar daarvoor. Dit resultaat is mede een gevolg van de verbeterde terugkeersamenwerking met Marokko en de inzet in het kader van het remigratiebeleid. Wij zijn als DTenV tevreden met de resultaten.” Email received on 28-5-2024, entitled: “Stand van de Uitvoering DTenV 2023; goede resultaten, complexer werk”

considered an (infra)structural dynamic at large. This was particularly clear with the way the Last Minute Team was invented at Schiphol Airport. Most interviewees referred to last-minute repeated asylum claims, or attempts to legally prevent forced removals as “vliegtuigtrapaanvragen” (literally translated as: applications from the stairs of the airplane),

But considering the vliegtuigtrapaanvragen, we found something. We organized an IND ‘last minute application team’. They can process these claims immediately in such a way that these people still enter the plane immediately” (DTenV regievoerder 3)

Interestingly, even though the particular IND office at Schiphol exists for about ten years, the ‘we found something’ expression of the DTenV regievoerder stresses the common goal of the state authorities in this respect.

Finally, the strategizing of DTenV regievoorders involves many other actors. In terms of return counseling, they often contact Vluchtelingenwerk or IOM to get involved. Vice versa, many NGOs offering return counseling indicated how they turn to the DTenV in case their tickets cannot be booked in the usual way (via IOM) (Interview NGO Return Assistance 2) or in case they have the impression that the to-be-returned migrant needs some extra financial stimuli to actually return (Interview NGO Return Assistance 3). Also in the detention center, we were told how the DTenV and IOM are coordinating their concrete operational practices of booking flights (Textbox 1), and with these examples we enter the dimension of relational work.

Box 1: Book your flight before mine: Time, forced removal and booking flights

Migrants who face a forced removal from the pre-removal detention center may decide to opt for the ‘assisted return’ option of IOM, also operating from the same detention center. The standardized practice then is that IOM arranges the return and books a flight for the to-be-returned migrant, but as a “back-up” the DTenV books a second flight a few days after the ‘assisted return flight’ arranged by the IOM (DTenV regievoerder 1). DTenV regievoorders stated they cannot simply broaden the timeframe they work with, as they have a legal obligation to keep detention to a minimum length, and the laissez-passers are not valid for ever. Time politics is indeed a crucial element of DTenV’s practices (Cleton 2022). Occasionally, migrants decide to opt for the IOM’s assisted return option rather last minute (as they realize a forced removal may occur soon). This then creates some administrative gymnastics between DTenV and IOM. In this example below, the regievoorders starts from the situation that a migrant is forcibly removed in four days time:

So I have your travel papers, and I have a [coerced] flight option in four days time for you, but you now say you would like to opt for the assisted return with IOM? Then I cannot delay the flight to 8 days or so. I might want to do that, but legally I am not allowed to do this. In this case, I *must* book the flight that departs in four days. But we can switch gears quickly with the IOM. That is the beauty of it as we, luckily, have \$\$\$ working here, a very practical oriented person. From the IOM. He might has its own boundaries, but we can really collaborate with him. So he knows we give him the chance to arrange an assisted return for this person. But only on the condition that his flight departs prior to *our flight*. IOM has wider possibilities to book flights, as for us it is administrated as a forced removal, and not every flight operator is willing to have these people on board, or they say, OK we facilitate this, but only once a week.

So in these particular cases, migrants may board a plane with IOM, which would be considered an ‘assisted return’. If s/he is in the end not boarding that flight, s/he will still be removed with the flight that was initially booked by the DTenV. This is a very concrete example of how assisted return and

forced removal are not clear divides, but rather a continuum of practices. As Wissink (2021) argues, this operational practice may potentially cause some miscounting, as one interviewee outlines for her case:

With regard to the annual figures, for example: someone is prepared as an “unaccompanied deportee” but refuses [to leave], but later departs with an escort [on another flight]. Both [flights] will be counted as a deportation: because the file is indeed booked on the plane every single time, it is registered and prepared. (Wissink 2021, p. 259)

In terms of **relational work**, it is relevant to think of internal DTenV dynamics first. For instance, when a migrant lacks the proper documents to put a return in practice, regievoorders contact the DIA department. Regievoorders can “put them to work” by, for instance, requesting a migrant presentation to embassies or consulates to determine the nationality of a person.⁵⁹ That particular person is then transported by DV&O from a detention centre, family location or AZC to a particular diplomatic space. At times, especially when migrants refuse to enter the DV&O vehicle, DIA attempts to invite the state representative to the locations where the particular migrant is held. In case of a forced removal, there are also all kinds of administrative relations forged as stated by staff of the Booking Department in a magazine of the migratieketen⁶⁰:

When the regievoorder has submitted the flight request, an administrative employee of the Bookings department [of DTenV] analyses it. The flight request is then sent to the Royal Military Police (KMar) for assessment. The KMar assesses whether escort assistance from KMar is necessary for the flight for the sake of safety. It is important that a well-considered decision is made here. That is why the DTenV always submits the flight request in the event of forced departure to the KMar, which has the right expertise to decide on the use of assistance. We, the Bookings department, then request the flight from the travel agent. The travel agent books the flight for the migrant. We then receive the final flight details from the travel agent. The director informs the migrant and his lawyer and transfers the flight details. We transfer the incoming travel documents to the KMar.

The relational work of DTenV regievoorders becomes more complicated is in cases where medical assistance is required. Then regievoorders contact, next to DIA and Booking Department, the so-called Extraordinary Departure department [Bijzonder Vertrek].⁶¹ Next to these DTenV departments, they also involve particular health-related services outside the DTenV [see Textbox 2]. The latter involves a rather complex landscape of do’s and don’ts in terms of data sharing. This is indicated by Appendix 5.

Finally, in terms of intra-DTenV relations, there are vertical relations between regievoorders and their superiors. DTenV regievoorders we spoke to indicated that they did not so much feel monitored or controlled by their superiors regarding every step they take in procedures. At the same time, we heard how occasionally senior DTenV staff attends the return conversation of

⁵⁹ In 2023, the DTenV asked representatives of third countries 2020 times to confirm a person’s nationality. In 1060 cases, the nationality was confirmed by the authorities DTenV (2023).

⁶⁰ [Samen regelen we terugkeer | Migratieketen](#), accessed on 9-1-2025

⁶¹ In some cases, returns are operationalized from hospital spaces from where the migrant is medically prepared to return, see [Verhalen uit de praktijk | Over DTenV | Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek](#), accessed on 30-9-2024

regievoorders with the to-be-returned migrant [Interview DTenV regievoerder 3]. Another vertical relation that matters is when permission needs to be granted to stretch the financial means to return a particular person. Several DTenV regievoorders indicated how they sometimes write “internal notas” that ask for more financial space that might convince the migrant to return. This nota is then sent to their superior (or even the manager of the particular superior). These notas are written from all locations we visited.

Box 2: Fit to fly, medical assistance and escorts

Health concerns of the to-be-returned migrant might become rather central to the work of DTenV regievoorders. Below, a DTenV regievoerder outlines ‘the doings’ in these cases.

Interviewer: In case of unusual conditions, such as health concerns, I assume that regievoorders need to arrange a lot before the vans of DV&O are parked here? How do you arrange assistance? Who to contact?

DTenV regievoerder: Well actually we have our own independent organization we work with. Medicare. We can ask for doctors or nurses. So in case I know of health concerns, I make sure medical assistance is present here, but I also make sure medical assistance, a nurse or doctor, is present during the flight. I can also check whether somebody is “fit to fly”, whether they are actually allowed to fly. But like I told you before, with the mother of a family I told you about, I cannot work with a statement of a general practitioner (GP). Her GP indicated she could not fly due to health concerns. But can I fully rely on this statement? No, that is a reason for me to hire a doctor from Medicare who can visit the person to check whether she is actually able to fly.

Interviewer: And why can't you trust the GP's statement?

DTenV regievoerder: Well, I don't know the GP. I don't know whether he knows the criteria to fly. He might not know all the things we can arrange for the flight. And, well the fit-to-fly-doctor we work with, he has a strong connection with us [“kort lijntje”]. Although he is independent, he knows like OK they can arrange this during the flight. If we need to, we can simply arrange all the things that are required. So he [the fit-to-fly doctor] can declare, the woman is able to fly, but two nurses should accompany and assist her during the flight. ... I collect all the information, about the medicines people take for instance, but I cannot evaluate this information. And when the actual flight is booked, I contact Medicare with the question: what do you think? To be honest, I don't want to carry that responsibility. I more or less stay out of this decision, as I am not a medical specialist. ... Usually when I have small signals that there are medical concerns, then I won't take the risk and ask for medical consultation. But sometimes you struggle with this, because you ask yourself: how serious is this issue? Should I really consult a doctor for this?

This fragment exemplifies the relational work of DTenV regievoorders, being the connector and monitoring actor of return processes. Interestingly, they have their standardized contacts to bring in medical expertise. Hence, they rely on an actor that is fully aware of the infrastructuring capacity of DTenV (i.e. what they can arrange before, during and after the flight). It is also relevant to note that this regievoerder first makes sure the ticket of the return flight is booked, and from there medical checks and facilities are arranged. So in this case the question does not seem to be whether a person is able to return, but rather what medical facilities are needed to put this return in practice. In a reaction to this report, the DTenV stated that this particular order (first booking/then health checks) is certainly not the case for all medical situations. It depends, for example, whether the migrant is governed by regievoorders from the Directorate of Support and Preparation [Directie Ondersteuning

en Voorbereiden Terugkeer] or the more stringent regime of Supervision and Measures [Toezicht en Maatregelen]. Moreover, there are many cases in which it is known beforehand that medical support is needed. In these cases, regievoerders should indicate, already at the moment when they contact the Booking Department of DTenV, that medical support is needed. For the sake of ‘pace and efficiency’ [“voortvarendheid”], especially in settings of detention, the regievoerders might indeed occasionally book the flight and then arrange a fit-to-fly assessment, as in the example above.

In the setting of pre-removal detention, DTenV regievoerders are closely collaborating with medical services on a more regular basis. One of them referred to this particular carceral space as a “mini-city” with all kinds of medical and social infrastructures. Another interviewee indicated how the attention for medical and psychological situations has intensified over years. Regievoerders in the detention centre meet every week with a team of psychologists, spiritual caregivers [“geestelijke verzorgers”] and heads of departments to discuss the extraordinary cases [“bijzondere cases”]. These meetings are important in order to be able to anticipate extra arrangements for the actual return/removal. The DTenV regievoerders indicated that they were not only responsible for arranging the care and security during the return flight, but also for arranging the medical transfer in the country of return. One of the practical challenges for DTenV regievoerders is to arrange all the medical services under time pressure, and they are faced with some information barriers due to professional secrecyes of health professionals. As one interviewee indicated:

“Ah, OK, there is some medical condition in this case. The medical service should know all about this. But, well, they have their professional secrecy [“beroepsgeheim”], oh that is fine, but I still need to arrange this [“ja dat is leuk, maar ik moet het wel regelen!]. If I would do nothing, then this creates trouble.”

From Rotterdam detention centers, and in case medical conditions ask for it, to-be-returned migrants are accompanied by health professionals of Medicare. In terms of an assisted return, DV&O arranges the transport, in terms of a forced removal, KMar is involved with an extra-securitized transport to the airport. As one respondent indicated, there are cases that involves an “entire apparatus” to deport one particular person. He explained in the situation of a forced removal with medical assistance that there might be two or three people assisting the person for health reasons. But in terms of long flights that includes transits, the Dutch labour law [arbeidstijdenwet] intervenes in the process. As a consequence, there might be six KMar agents escorting the migrant [in addition to the medical services]: two on the first flight, two others during transit, and again two others might be involved in the last stage of the journey. As this interviewee concludes: “[such operation] heavily extracts the pool of staff of KMar” [“dat trekt dus eventjes een wissel op het personeel wat ze daar hebben!”]. To return families, we heard a similar number of KMar staff involved in one single escort.

The sharing of information is pivotal for the everyday functioning of the RMI. In terms of regievoerders’ relational work, the before mentioned Lokale Ketenoverleggen (LKO) are important for the formation of return strategies. Like any other formal organization, the state-related partners of the LKO - DTenV, COA and IND - need to comply to the EU guidelines on personal data protection (known as AVG in the Netherlands). It is worth noting that particular sensitive data are particularly protected by these guidelines, including among others, political preferences, health, biometric data, ethnicity and religion.⁶² In DTenV’s internal guidelines on the sharing of data, it is explicitly stated that the AVG applies to the automated/digital processing of data, but that it excludes oral consultations and discussions. When we attended

⁶² See also: [Informatieuitwisseling en privacy | Over DTenV | Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek](#), accessed on 9-1-2025. It is worth noting that formally different rules apply to police forces.

one of the LKO meetings, we learned that rather detailed descriptions on people's procedure, health situation, legal navigations of that person can be shared. It was particularly interesting to see how DTenV regievoorders and COA case managers were combining fragments of information in order to decide or materialize return strategies. Next to these formalized practices of information sharing during meetings, informal connections and close work relations are crucial in this respect. While the internal DTenV guidelines on information sharing asks for reluctance about the sharing of data, these informal channels matter in the everyday setting, as one regievoerder explained:

If you work in Ter Apel (the national asylum application center), you really see people for the first time fresh, but here at the AZC there is a *file*, and you have discussed the case at the LKO. And you know that they have talked to COA, and you know how this conversation went, what they told them [COA case managers] ... At times people can be very open, and they have said things to COA, but they don't want to talk to me, and I have to accept it. But then you simply approach COA and ask how the conversation went.

Through this bricolaging of information by DTenV regievoorders, the different roles of COA case managers (as trust persons for asylum seekers) and DTenV regievoorders are merged. In the same way, Vluchtelingenwerk (the national Refugee Council) – a non-governmental body – is used as a valuable source of information by the DTenV.

We are all based on the same location. Coincidentally, the case we discussed this morning [referring to the LKO meeting], the single mother, this is really a collaboration between Vluchtelingenwerk, DTenV and COA. When I had a return conversation with her, I immediately ran to Vluchtelingenwerk, like hey, this is the situation now, what could you do in this case? What can we together do in this case? In these situations, you are really looking for each other. For the real communication, we have the LKOs, but I can also simply knock this door [pointing to the door separating the COA office and DTenV office]. You do discuss a lot with each other (DTenV regievoerder 3).

A colleague working at a family location confirmed this by saying:

The good thing about the LKO is that you hear all kinds of new things from COA staff, because they know the people much better than we do. They only see them much more often. Then we hear about their wellbeing, because the case managers also have their own return conversations, and we hear about what keep their mind busy these days. So you keep each other up to date. And this collaboration is very pleasant (DTenV regievoerder 4).

The reverse is also true, as Vluchtelingenwerk also contacts DTenV regievoorders who often work close in geographical terms:

DTenV is important for us, especially in the Family location and VBL. At the VBL, they just work above us. Vluchtelingenwerk sits downstairs, and DTenV is right above us, so you can simply walk to them, and ask "who is the regievoerder of Huppeldepup? ... [This proximity] works really well, because you can really *collaborate* to properly return a client ["om een client goed terug te krijgen naar een land van herkomst"] ... or it is important to indicate that we need more time, to prevent them making a joyful jump because they can start the deportation process, that would be painful.

These interviews illustrate that indeed informality plays an important role in making the formal rules work (e.g. Borrelli and Lindberg 2024). These formal and informal ways of information sharing might be very practical for DTenV regievoorders, they also raise serious ethical concerns for some people in these settings. This is particularly the case for the COA case managers as well as Vluchtelingenwerk staff members who are present at asylum locations as they play the role of trust persons. The fact that these different actors share the same location stimulate informal exchanges and socialization processes which in turn create some potential for the building of epistemic communities. Unlike Vluchtelingenwerk staff, COA case managers carry the official mandate to put in practice migration policy, including return policies. This creates an inherent crux of being both a trust person for people living in asylum locations, while also informing return strategies that are coordinated by DTenV regievoorders. COA case managers, as well as Vluchtelingenwerk staff members, might encounter dilemmas in terms of what to share and when to share with DTenV. In so doing, the epistemic community is not without boundaries and friction. For example, some COA managers who are considered trust persons of migrants shared with us that they feel at times discomfort and “ethical conflicts” in case the return strategy outlined is ‘pre-removal detention’. In these situations, the DTenV directs COA staff to discontinue any conversation with the people in question, as any sign pointing to a forced removal might be a reason for migrants to leave and disappear under the radar. One example was shared by COA case manager 2:

There was a case, and we knew the strategy was to put them in detention when they got a negative outcome. But these people came to me continuously, because you also have built a relationship with them over years. So they come to me and report on things, also on their legal outcome. They wanted to have another appointment, another conversation. But I knew there was a serious consequence for them, and the DTenV asked me to not get in to conversation with them. At that time, I struggled ethically with myself. ... There is an ethical boundary [ethische grens].

Thus, from this interview fragment we may conclude that frictions may not only emerge between actors, but also within the same person.

The last type of *doing* we put forward is the administrative work. The paperwork involved can be seen as the signature of the state in which potential dilemmas, inconsistencies and arbitrariness in the governing of returns are straightjacketed (Borelli and Lindberg 2019). To discuss this further, it is worthwhile to state that the aforementioned return strategy is filed carefully in the software system by the DTenV regievoorders. The question of legal deportability is crucial here, and the bureaucratic proof of someone’s legal deportability is based on the individualized file-making of regievoorders in particular software systems (see Section 5.3). The file digitally travels with the migrant in case of transfers. For instance, when a family is transferred from a regular AZC to a family location or when a male asylum seeker is sent to a detention center, a new DTenV regievoorder at the other end takes over the file. Our interviewees indicated that they critically study the file when they first encounter it. As one interviewee explained:

Personally, in my view the quality of the return strategies [“vertrekplannen”] vary considerably. There is no fixed structure, and that is OK, but there are colleagues copying

kinds of meaningless information to the form just for the sake of filling the form⁶³ ... For me, when I study the files the most important starting point is the digital file in Sharepoint. There I can look at the previous return conversations led by the previous regievoerder. *THERE* I learn about what has been said, what emotions are at play, and there I learn where the pain is [for the migrant]. These reports are *gold* for us. (DTenV regievoerder 5)

This interview indicates that documented files are filtered and re-interpreted by the next regievoerder in line. In studying the file, it may be the case that the new regievoerders deviate from the previous return strategy, as one regievoerder indicated:

In my case, if my ‘fingerspitzengefühl’ is saying that the previous regievoerder has been on the wrong track, I will change direction and opt for a different approach (DTenV regievoerder 4).

This flexibility is tied to the earlier outlined instructions for regievoerders to take initiative’ and ‘to be creative’.

Basically all DTenV regievoerders indicated that the administrative tasks have multiplied over years and have become increasingly complex. Some indicated that all these tasks feed the monitoring role of the organization at large, which was considered to be positive by some, while for others, the administrative load is a disturbing development, as one interviewee complained:

We have to keep so many lists, and we need to set so many check marks (“vinkjes”) in the system. Look – we are *regievoerders* – and we exist because we generate departures. Preferably on a voluntary basis, but if this is not possible, then with force. *That is our job*. That is also the *commonality* of ‘we the DTenV’ – that is why *we* do this. We are a *return organization*. But what we see today is that our own department BIT – that is the computer-led department in The Hague – that department has grown significantly, and it is still growing significantly. And from there, more control mechanisms come into play. Like “you have to put that check mark right” or “that aspect is not in the right place”. From our view, all this work does not contribute to the departure of the migrant, but it does swallow us (“het slokt ons op”) to continuously put the right check marks. And that is to me a very big obstacle to my work (DTenV regievoerder 5)

The BIT [Business and Information Technology] department this respondent is referring to is the department that arranges the buy-in and maintenance of ICT-products at DTenV. They might be an easy target for intra-organizational critique regarding the increase of administrative loads, but it is important to realize that many of the check marks in the forms and software programmes depend on changes in law or priorities at the level of the Ministry as well.

⁶³ The actual document that is called the vertrekplan does have a clear structure with different sections to fill out such as a stepwise plan to departure, agreements with the to-be-returned migrant and agreements with chain partners, this includes the agreements of the LKO meetings, mentioned earlier.

Finally, with the administrative work, there comes a lot of time planning and the space to maneuver for regievoorders become more confined, as DTenV regievoorders 5 continued in the interview:

We can actually never put someone in detention spontaneously. Never! Just imagine, someone is found being here illegally, and we do *have everything* to return him... that is impossible because the “uitvoerend ambtenaar” needs to be planned WEEKS in advance, de Royal Army and the escorts, they have to be planned WEEKS in advance. It can never be arranged on an ad-hoc basis (DTenV regievoerder 5).

And, his colleague added:

And for us [at a family location] it is extra complicated since families cannot stay longer in detention than two weeks. So you have to make sure that the flight departs in these two weeks, you need to be sure KMar is available, everything has to be there in place in these two weeks (DTenV regievoerder 4).

In other words, dealing with time pressure or different tempos is an inherent aspect of DTenV regievoorders. In fact, as Cleton (2022) convincingly shows, the pace of actions of migration governance is of crucial importance in terms of understanding migration control. Especially in the setting of the family locations, this time pressure may appear rather sudden to these case workers. A family might actually stay in this location for years and their lives stagnate, and this pauses a lot of the activities of regievoorders, until the moment the authorities can materialize a return (e.g. because of changes in diplomatic relations or because of the appearance of a travel paper, or because of a charter flight arranged by Frontex), and then everything should be arranged within a limited time period. On the other hand, seemingly straightforward timelines might be disrupted by legal contestations of people’s return process (e.g. when people in detention apply for a residence permit).

5.3. Materialities & technologies

For this study, we also include the materialities and technologies that co-construct the Dutch RMI. The analytical difficulty is to demarcate this dimension. For instance, in all asylum locations we have visited, we have seen material traces of other actors in the field. As there have been folders, posters and telephone numbers of NGOs, support programmes and return counselling. We also noted that we could broaden the analysis of security staff at the locations, but it is undoable to discuss every aspect in detail. Also because the family location, detention center and regular AZC vary considerably. Hence we decide to focus on three prominent elements: **rooms for return conversations, transportation, material support to return, and use of software and high technology.**

The AZC we visited is a permanent AZC since 1994 and the accommodation consists of 7 buildings (former military terrain) with approximately 400 beds available, it is located in a thriving urban neighbourhood, with a primary school next door. From this location, return processes are coordinated by the DTenV and close collaboration with COA case managers. For these actors, one important space is the conversation room. For some COA case managers, who work on the basis of a trust relation, the physical space is seen as a barrier to their work:

The conversation rooms are really empty, very sober. The chairs are fixated. The distance to the table is not very comfortable for the residents. The height of the chair is also far from comfortable. The priority is clearly security, and not whether somebody feels

comfortable to talk. The distance to the Interpreter Telephone [tolkentelefoon], basically everything is fixated. I cannot change anything. ... and there is this screen right in our middle, and when you have three interlocutors, you cannot see one of them because of the balk in the middle ... I remember how I started working here, with just a regular chair and a regular table [COA Case Manager 1].

Box 3: A material continuum

Below we present three conversation rooms located at the regular AZC we visited. The first is considered the most open and comfortable space for trustful conversations, the second is seen as a discomfortable room, but according to the COA case managers still warmer for its decoration (the paintings), the third is the most clinical space and seen as the space that expresses the most authority.

The open conversation room [no screens and no doors separating clients from authorities].

The COA conversation room

The DTenV conversation room

For the DTenV regievoerder the same conversation room had a different meaning. For him, it was an important requirement to have a large table with sufficient distance, and that there is literally a space for him “to escape”. The difference in need for security can be explained for the different roles DTenV regievoorders embody, as in their experience, many migrants view them as the evil source that forces them to leave, and this leads to angry expressions and frustrations. All interviewees making use of similar spaces had their own tactics to deal with them. Some COA case managers, for example, look for more convivial spaces to talk to their clients (outside, in their rooms, or shared living spaces). Some DTenV regievoorders leave the door open that separates them from the migrant. This mainly happens when they perceive they have a good relation with the to-be-returned migrant. In the detention center, we spoke to one regievoerder who – against the protocol – sits at the same side of separation screen to create a social atmosphere of closeness, if the situation allows for it. Thus, some material aspects of RMIs are actively bended by the actors involved. In the future, this bending of spaces might work automatically, as indicated in the presentation of the “Conversation Room of the Future” (see Textbox 4).

Box 4: The conversation room of the future. Hi-tech micro infrastructures

In October 2023, the DTenV organized its first Wetenschapsevent. This first time public event aims to bring together scientific insights and the daily realities of DTenV. The thematic focus of the day was *behaviour*, and it consisted of all kinds of sessions varying from intercultural dialogues to a lecture on motivating decision-making, and an interaction session on ethical questions (led by a specialist from Ministry of Defense). During this day, various designs of the ‘conversation room of the future’ were presented by the Technical University of Delft and a design/development company (a project launched by COA, and co-funded by the EU). This particular design below caught our attention, as its strikingly different from the current rooms that are used. The design of the room strives to create a safe space and the organic shapes seek to create comfort. We were told by the presenters that the light automatically becomes brighter in case a heated debate unfolds or somebody becomes angry or ‘very emotional’. The brighter light would make the person in question more docile, the argument was.

The transportation of to-be-returned migrants also comes with considerable material differences. As underlined by Walters et al. (2021) and Walters (2018) materiality reflects the “asymmetrical struggles” of migration regimes versus migrants. This is clearly reflected in the vehicles and materials used by DV&O to transport migrants.

As stated above, DV&O arranges all kinds of transport. Some DTenV regievoerder simply called them *taxis*. To indicate this, we present some general information about the involvement of DV&O for the year 2023. In 2023, the DV&O handled some 16.642 transport requests for the entire migration chain, including the realm of return migration. These requests include for example 958 retour services for so-called ‘migrant presentations’ (e.g. transporting migrant to an embassy to confirm his/her identity) (Interview DV&O). It also includes 700 coerced transport requests from an AZC to the pre-removal detention centers

(DV&O n.d., p. 28). Of these 700 requests, only 500 of these transports actually materialized.⁶⁴ In addition, 127 transport have been executed with the destination ‘Gesloten Inrichting Zeist [the closed family location] (Interview DV&O). In practice, the DTenV requests transport from DV&O through the Infodesk, and DV&O executes a risk assessment based on the file constructed by DtenV regievoorders. DV&O considers the information they receive for this assessment as ‘broad’ and it includes information regarding the ‘insluititel’ [the legal grounds for their transport], whether a migrant is expected to ‘collaborate’ with the transport, the mental condition of the migrant, the ‘position’ or opinion of the migrant vis-à-vis the transport (including removals). The DV&O usually opts between regular transport and extra securitized transport (DV&O n.d.). These are compartmentalized vehicles with room for two or three DV&O officers inside the vehicle. In case of extra securitized transport, the vehicle is unlabeled (so without any DV&O sign) and there are usually three officers put on one individual migrant. In case of exceptional situations, such as a precarious health situation, DV&O might also opt for a so-called Luxe2 or Luxe3 transport. The latter concerns vehicles without compartments and with extra material arrangements for health-related concerns

According to DtenV regievoorders the appearance of DV&O staff varies according to the level of coercion. When it concerns an arrest (“staandehouding”) and coerced transfer to pre-removal detention, DV&O appear as forceful police agents in uniform and with bodycams (DV&O n.d.) (see also Figure 3 below). The appearances occur in the early morning to surprise the migrant in question and to prevent turmoil with the other residents. The number of DV&O agents also vary:

Depending on the risks I indicate, they decide on their staffing. For instance, I can indicate this person is generally quiet, and he is quite old. Then they generally show up with 4 people. When it is a bigger family, then they just add up [“dan gaan ze gewoon plussen”], and they easily shift to two vans. Sometimes, I see two vans for just one person (DTenV regievoerder 3).

Thus, the more risks there are reported by DTenV in the files, the more force is used by the actors in the RMI. The most extreme case is outlined in the Textbox below.

⁶⁴ From the DV&O data, we can trace 161 cancellations of coerced transports on day 0. Although the annual report of DV&O explains this with the reason that people have disappeared before they arrive, their written reaction on this issue states that “these 161 cancellations *should not* be interpreted as ‘left with destination unknown’ [Met Onbekende Bestemming Vetrokken / MOB].

Figure 3: Images of a coerced removal. Source: DV&O staff (DV&O n.d.) / Photos of DV&O vehicles by Joris

Box 5: Materiality of extreme force

Recently, [a video](#) by the anti-deportation protest group MiGReat has explicitly revealed the use of enforcement and violence in a forced removal of a Syrian man to Bulgaria (Video accessed on 26-9-2024). This video shows how the Royal Army in plainclothes held the man with strong force, hands and legs cuffed and fixated by tie-rips and seat belts, while the man screaming and desperately asking for oxygen (with muffled sound as his face was held by the Royal Army). The video also discloses that the medical staff assisting the removal approached the person filming the situation and asks her to sit down with the argument that “this is the only moment the Syrian man can resist, once we are flying he will calm down.” The woman with the camera refused to sit down. In its public response, the Royal Army declared that the removal has been ‘regular’ [“de uitzetting is op reguliere wijze verlopen”].⁶⁵ In media reports after this incident, it is stated that the Royal Army can make use of body cuffs and jaw clamps. One interviewee of DTenV narrated the process and the use of most forceful methods. The narration starts in the detention centre Rotterdam, the day before the actual flight. It concerns a situation where the DTenV perceives the person a risk to himself based on, for instance, previous outcries of committing suicide.

There is a x-number of people willing to assist you downstairs by fair means (“goedschiks”), if this is not possible, you go down *horizontally* [meaning you are carried by the law enforcers]. Downstairs, you are undressed, and you are put in a *scheurjurk* [special clothes that preventing people of doing harm]. ... You are thus completely stripped. You have nothing with you, and you are in clothes provided by DJI. Then, yes you are put in an isolation cell. The following day, you are put on *extra securitized transport* of DV&O. They put you in this “scheurkleding” in the van. They handcuff you. You can walk with them, if you refuse, you end up in the van *horizontally*. Then you are brought to the royal army. Under supervision, you are provided your regular clothes again to board the plane. There again, you are informed about the procedures and your options. In the most extreme cases, they can, in addition to the handcuffs, use a kind of special tool that you sometimes see on American TV shows, fixating your hands and legs. In case the person spits, or something like that, they may put on a kind of mask to prevent that. And then you board the plane. The royal police would first ask permission to board the plane, they go through the backdoor, not via the regular platform, or regular trunk. This is the most extreme situation.

⁶⁵ [Zeldzame beelden van gedwongen uitzetting Syriër: ‘Hoever willen we gaan?’ | Binnenland | AD.nl](#), accessed on 26-9-2024

After the above incident with the Syrian man, questions have been raised about deportation and the use of force in the Dutch Parliament. The minister responded by saying that for the year 2024 the body cuff was used in 101 cases, a beenband (immobilizing velcro) has been used and in 65 cases KMar used tiewraps to forcibly remove a migrant.

In case of some medical concerns, materiality might play a crucial, but complicated role. This was particularly well illustrated by the following case starting with a man in a wheelchair:

Ah, so, this man is in a wheelchair. No problem, we have a wheelchair here. But it is a wheelchair of this location, so it suffices until we reach the DV&O van, but the wheelchair should stay here. ... So at the G-Pier (of Schiphol Airport) we need another wheelchair. So we need to arrange it. Well that works fine in the airplane. That wheelchair, however, is a Dutch wheelchair, so it should come back in some way to Amsterdam. So in country x, we have to arrange a wheelchair or perhaps a taxi... or whatever works over there. We should arrange all this. It is maybe not us, the regievoerder literally arranging this, but we have to *signal* it and direct all bits and pieces to the right person. I mean, we have our Booking Department, they can set in motion quite some things. We have our Medical Service, they can arrange quite some things, like the correct number of medication. Then we have a special unit of DIA, which is called Bijzonder Vetrekk [Extraordinary Departures]. If there is a need for a particular reception in the country of origin – varying from that wheelchair question to an ambulance to psychiatric facilities to a clinic to a kidney diagnosis – just in this extreme case [of a kidney diagnosis], you cannot simply say, well country X good luck with it!, no then you are simply too late with the kidney dialysis. You just have to arrange these things.

Infrastructuring returns thus often implies connecting materials to make returns happen, and there is a special department of DTenV - ‘Extraordinary Departures’ - specialized in this. In a rather different way, materials may also help to convince migrant to opt for assisted returns. Here, it is relevant to take into account the work of particular NGOs offering material or in-kind support to their clients. Stichting Wereldwijd is one particular organization having its roots in catholic humanitarianism of the 1980s. They run their project called WereldTools aiming to “*help people in a practical manner*” and to prevent they “*return home empty handed*” by offering materials, tools, machines (often second-hand) that are shipped to them in a large box once they have returned to their country of origin. Their programme has been praised by one IOM officer we interviewed as the “only NGO that has added value” in the field of return. Other NGOs have a more informal and ad-hoc approach to additional material support as they occasionally collect and offer second hand telephones or laptops to their clients when they return.

But not all materials can be transferred to locations people are sent to. In fact, one practical challenge in the process of various transfers in the RMI are the **material leftovers**. In terms of a pre-removal detention, the to-be-returned migrant might get time to change clothes and maybe to bring things for the first day, but that is basically it. All the other material belongings are left behind in the asylum locations people resided in. After the migrant left the place, these materials are packed by COA staff, and some of the belongings are brought to the people in different locations. These belongings are again transported by the DV&O: “Again the taxis” as one of the respondents commented. One COA case manager indicated the material leftovers have a reason:

When people are sent to a family location, they can only bring 20kg of belongings. Why is this the case? Well, because you are going to fly in a few days. And then people think like HUH!? Then I say, yes the intention is in the end you are really leaving. But the people collect so much stuff! It is abnormal. I sometimes think, how does all this fit in these small rooms?... But if you think about it, it is quite logical as they spend three or four years here [COA case manager 2].

COA locations have particular spaces reserved for the material leftovers. In the asylum location we visited, this was known as the MOB-hok, named after the term *met onbekende bestemming vertrokken* (left with destination unknown). In the family location, this space was a big container just outside the location. After a couple of months, these material leftovers are brought to a waste station, unless somebody is picking them up. With some amazement, COA case managers and DTenV regievoorders referred to a case whereby a recently removed person from South-East Asia came back to the Netherlands rather quickly, just a few weeks after his removal, to collect some of his belongings. The person entered the central application center in Ter Apel and visited the family location to collect his belongings. One DTenV regievoorders jokingly stated that they have become the Circulation Service instead of Departure Service, as this person entered another asylum space and will most likely encounter DTenV regievoorders very soon to work on his return.

As a final dimension of the RMI we discuss the high technology and software systems involved. In terms of technology, it is crucial to note that the search of identity confirmation is a central challenge for return processes and at the very start of the asylum procedure, there is the intake by AVIM which involves high technologies that may be useful later in the governing of return (see also Leurs 2023). As one DTenV regievoorder explained the case of somebody refusing to provide the code to access his mobile telephone to AVIM:

So you are saying you are this person, OK, so could you give me the code ... Ah, OK, so you don't want to give the code, well, then we connect it to our software and the device will be read ["dan wordt die gewoon aan software gehangen en dat ding wordt uitgelezen"]. Not only everything that is saved on the device, no they can also read everything that has been deleted at some time [DTenV regievoorder 2].

In terms of the use of administrative software it is somewhat confusing that some systems receive different names from different organisations, and some interviewees referred to previously used software, while others used the new name. For the state actors involved, there are shared platforms, but also boundaries that hamper information sharing. The DTenV regievoorders mainly work with ISTV [Informatiesysteem Terugkeer en Vertrek], but their work also involve other software systems like TULP (from DJI in the detention center), EUVIS (EU Visa System)⁶⁶, SIGMA (information platform for migration chain partners), RIAT system of Frontex.⁶⁷ For DTenV regievoorders, all relevant case information appears in ISTV: from

⁶⁶ EUVIS is particularly used for identification matters. As DTenV regievoorder 2 indicated: "So when I apply for a visa for a Schengen country, then I will be registered. [As authority], you can fill out a lot there, before you provide a yes or no. As a person, you need to show who you are – your identity – including your travel papers. Regardless the visa is granted or not, all this information could be filled in already. Due to European rules and AVG, these informations cannot stay endless in the system, but the *hit* might still be there."

⁶⁷RIAT is a digital platform of Frontex, called the Reintegration Assistance Tool (RIAT), and owned by the European Commission. It is described as "an online tool simplifies and standardises the exchange of information on the reintegration process to the best benefit of third country nationals, reintegration partners and Member States. It provides an end-to-end live overview of the case, including the application, the development and

the very first AVIM hearing, to EURODAC information, to police reports are accessible there. The personalized V-number [vreemdelingsnummer] – a kind of ID-number – is crucial for this system. DTenV regievoorders also referred to Vreemdeling in Beeld (others called it SIGMA) that they may consult through ISTV. This is considered to be a platform for information sharing of chain partners, like COA, KMar, DJI and AVIM. This may provide vital information for regievoorders, like health (not everything is visible due to privacy issues), contact details of lawyers or criminal records. Our interviews indicate that especially behavioral or situational information is interesting for DTenV regievoorders (DTenV Regievoerder 1, DtenV Regievoerder 2). Also relevant return information of ISTV feeds SIGMA.

Similarly COA case managers work with a country-wide system called IBIS [‘integraal bewoners informatie systeem’].⁶⁸ Here IND can add legal outcomes [‘beslissingen’], but cannot access the system and read reports of conversations between COA case managers and asylum seekers. However, the unsharing of information gets blurry because of the information bricolage we referred to earlier in this report. The IND is for example often present during LKOs and during these meetings, information is shared that are actually bounded in software programmes. A good example is the departure plan (“vertrekplan”), as one regievoerder stated:

[The departure plan] is an intern document. But we are of course sharing this information at LKO, and also in between, of course. You constantly run into each other, but the departure plan is in fact an internal document (DTenV regievoerder 5).

While the information sharing is in general well organized, the coupling of information between partners, in combination with the information boundaries that are set up – lead to administrative mistakes and fragmentation in some situations. One concrete example is that in case a migrant is sent from a COA-location (AZC, family location or emergency location) to a detention center, medical information does not automatically travel with the migrant, but follows within 24-hours. Consequently, a risk is that incidents happen in this time period or that health situations of migrants deteriorate.⁶⁹ Moreover, in case migrants do not give their consent to transfer all the medical data, staff members in the detention center are not fully informed (they are only informed about potential threatful behavior).

At times, this fragmentation of information becomes as crucial as the question of deportability. It is relevant to note here that in the Dutch RMI there are two bureaucratic terms related to the question of deportability. De ‘verwijderbaarheidstitel’ [literal translation: ‘removal title’] indicates the extent to which someone can be removed from the country. This is monitored and set by the IND. In addition to this, there is the question of ‘uitzetbaarheid’, which concerns the issue whether somebody is practically deportable. The second title is set by DTenV. For DTenV regievoorders the verwijderbaarheidstitel is visible in the ISTV system. IND sets the

approval of a reintegration plan, and the reporting. Also, it also serves as an important source of data for evaluation and quality monitoring purposes” see, [Reintegration assistance \(europa.eu\)](#), accessed on 15-10-2024.

⁶⁸ COA case managers also work with MYBUS, which is a more location-specific system coordinating tasks and information for COA staff working on the same asylum location.

⁶⁹ [Handreiking uitwisseling medische informatie in de vreemdelingenketen | Richtlijn | Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek](#), accessed on 9-1-2025.

removal title in their own system, and this is automatically visible for DTenV in ISTV. According to some of our respondents, it happens that such crucial information is put incorrect in the system or is left unchanged while there is in fact a significant legal change. Sometimes a successful appeal is administrated as an unsuccessful appeal in the system, leading to very different legal outcomes. Or an application for a residence permit is not visible in the ISTV system since it is not “asylum related”, which may create the situation that the DTenV regievoorders is unlawfully continuing return activities. As long as this regular application is running, the person in question is not deportable. Our respondents commented on these situations with words like:

Mistakes are made. This happens on a fairly regular basis [dat gebeurt best regelmatig] [DTenV medewerker 5].

As I said, this line of information is not always correct. So we have to check and carefully, and at times we need to simply call the IND [COA case manager 1]

We need to have more collective systems. I really don't understand that only in the Netherlands the Police has its own system, the IND has its own system, the Royal Police has its own system the DTenV has its own system ...It is really crazy [van de zotte] that information may disappear so easily when a migrant is moving from A to B. [DTenV regievoerder 2]

In one particular case of a previously failed removal], the DTenV was putting pressure on us, like ‘come on, this time it *should* work out, since we really want to remove her...and then, you won't believe it, it goes wrong exactly with them. DTenV did not arrange the escort, so the woman made a lot of turmoil in the plane for a second time. So the airline said, we won't take you. So we put everything in motion for nothing. *And the regievoerder respondend: Yes, it is real pity, the previous regievoerder did not report that the previous attempt went out of hand* [ja, echt balen want de vorige regievoerder had dit niet opgenomen, dat het de vorige keer ook was geescaleerd] [IND representative 2]

I have had conversations with people with the starting point: we can now deport you. Then this person really became very mad, because I was actually wrong. He said he was still in procedure. So then you call the *ketenservicelijn*, and it appears that the IND forgot to change the title. To fill that check box [dat vinkje te zetten] (DTenV regievoerder 4).

Eventual errors in the RMI is a sensitive issue in the Netherlands. In 2013, the Inspection Security and Justice wrote a report on the tragic case of Alexander Dolmatov⁷⁰ and highlighted some important shortcomings regarding the issue of information sharing between state authorities (see Brouwer and Middelkoop 2013). Since then, state agencies have sought ways to improve this issue. As a reaction to this report, the IND writes that “since 2015 the quality of residence- and removal titles [*verblijfs- en verwijderbaarheidstitels*] are continuously measured, and these insights show that the quality of these titles is in order.” Moreover, they indicate that changes in these titles are communicated with chain partners “once a day” [één

⁷⁰ Alexander Dolmatov committed suicide in a detention center. It appeared later that he was unlawfully detained in this pre-removal detention center (see Brouwer and Middelkoop 2013, p.41-42).

keer per dag] and that in complex cases one could scale up to a team called *Titel & Identiteit* that documents all kinds of knowledge regarding the residence and removal titles”. Besides this, the IND states there is the general agreement between chain partners [ketenpartners] to always execute checks by telephone calls when irreversible events are about to happen, like a forced removal. The responsibility of executing this check is put on the shoulders of those actor who is about to put the irreversible act in motion. In their reaction to this report, the DTenV confirmed the reading of the IND and highlighted that regievoorders can indeed call the *ketenserviceline* – a kind of service line for the entire migration chain. Moreover, before the actual removal occurs a final check is done by the Booking Department of DTenV.

While we do not question whether these mechanisms foregrounded by the IND’s and DTenV’s reactions are put in place, the interviews do nevertheless indicate that uncertainties or knowledge gaps may still emerge in the everyday experiences of case workers of the Dutch RMIs.

5.4. Relations: Synergies and frictions seen from the DTenV

We asked DTenV regievoorders on which partnerships they relied on, which actors made their work more difficult, and what relations are avoided in the daily operations of return migration governance. There are certain commonalities for all DTenV regievoorders, and the character of some relations depend heavily on the context they work from. Some commonalities across settings is that DTenV regievoorders rely heavily on the linguistic expertise of interpreters, the security and transport services offered by DTenV, the IND for the necessary information regarding deportability or the presence of travel papers, the Royal Police for supervision and escorts, the COA for questions of accommodation of refugees. The *vreemdelingenketen* is indeed a chain of operating actors with shared objectives. Beyond the state actors, most DTenV regievoorders collaborated with IOM for the reintegration assistance and consulted *Vluchtelingenwerk* for particular information. However – quite in contrast with the LVV programme (see Chapter 6) – very few DTenV regievoorders that work from COA locations or detention settings spoke about close relations with smaller NGOs offering return counselling. DTenV regievoorder generally stated that they generally do not collaborate with NGOs offering return assistance. For the detention center, our respondent answered: “basically, we don’t see them here. IOM is simply the biggest party, and they know the procedures inside the detention centre.”

While discussing the importance of relations in their daily work, some regievoorders zoomed out and articulated the importance of diplomatic relations, and hence referred to their international affairs department DIA, as a crucial link in their daily operations. The importance of return diplomacy is not only reflected in the return statistics, but also in the way international cooperations smoothens the return route, as one respondent working from detention indicated:

[Lately], we have a big group of Moroccans here, and the collaboration of Morocco on return has improved considerably. This means that their period in detention is shorter, and that they return more quickly ... Some time ago, this collaboration [with Morocco] was much more difficult, we then noticed that the periods of detention easily exceeded six months. When the positive turn in the collaboration with Morocco came, we have better reasons to prolong detentions [as removal is proven to be possible]. It is not only

about the agreements. Sometimes there are good agreements, but putting these agreements into practice is rougher [‘stroever’] (DTenV regievoerder 1).

Diplomatic relations affect the decisions and actions of DTenV regievoorders greatly. Cleton (2022), for instance, outlines how less time is spent on assisted return options when the forced removal can be achieved in relatively easy ways. On the other hand, some states express no interest in collaborations on Dutch return migration governance, which lead to non-response on identity requests or very long and ineffective procedures. Without exception, this lack of diplomatic collaborations causes a lot of frustration in the everyday work of DTenV regievoorders.

Concerning actors that contest the work of DTenV, all regievoorders immediately referred to lawyers as the main actor that oppose and challenge their daily practices. While some acknowledged the legal support of migrants as an inherent element of the ‘rechtsstaat’, other respondents hinted at a logic that lawyers play legal games to frustrate the system with negative effects for migrants too.

When they submit their repeated asylum claims (HASA), then I think that the lawyer realizes that this application will be ineffective. For sure, if it concerns a 3rd or 4th attempt. How many new factual circumstances may appear in these cases? But then of course, people are in the procedure for a long while. But we see here how these procedures suffocate them [the asylum seekers]. They don’t want to return, and therefore they start a new procedure. But...this uncertainty, and this waiting for another IND ruling, that will eat them [“dat gaat aan ze vreten”] (DTenV regievoerder 5).

In line with other state actors, advocacy groups are considered to be actors that contest the governing of return migration. This particularly relates to children’s rights, as NIDOS and Defense for Children have been mentioned frequently in our interviews. DTenV regievoerder 3 articulated the agonistic character of the RMI. He considered it a constant “battle” and stressed this by saying:

DTenV is at odds with Vluchtelingenwerk, is at odds with lawyers, and then there is NIDOS, you know. Then there is *suddenly* a repeated asylum application. Then we have to act, COA have to act, and in the end, a lot of work is created just for *one migrant*, and there are plenty of them. We all keep the system alive, and that costs a lot of money [“bakken met geld”]. You know, the lawyer is payed by government money, we are payed from government budgets, but we are diametrically opposed to each other [“we staan lijnrecht tegenover elkaar”]. Sometimes, this is just madness!

In this battle, shelter organizations are seen as a major actor that complicates the work of the DTenV. The same DTenV regievoerder explicitly explained his viewpoint how these organizations work against the system:

I don’t have contact with these organizations, zero. People can go *MOB* [leave the AZC without supervision], but then, of course, they stay there *super illegal* [“kei illegaal”]. I say, if people know beforehand that they can go there [to these shelter organizations], then it does not stimulate the pressure I want to put on them to go to the VBL. No. Then they prefer to move in this direction [of the shelter] ... Let me put it in this way, I don’t say it is bad that these organizations exist, but they do complicate my work, because I could have achieved more with this single woman when she realized that she *really would have ended up in the streets*.

In line with this ‘local communities’ and social networks of migrants’ are considered to be destabilizing actors too. Churches, football clubs, schools, journalists, doctors, neighbors, co-migrants, they all are part of a circuit that may provide escape routes for people living in irregularity or create a lot of turmoil and public exposure for *particular cases*, even though they themselves question the effectivity of their activities (see also Schapendonk 2024). While these opposing forces are sometimes framed as locally embedded actors, other interviewees acknowledged a European dimension of migrant positionality by referring to migrant supporting contacts in Spain, France, or Germany.

Evidently, the setting DTenV workers worked from matters here. From a pre-removal detention center, DTenV workers rely on an infrastructure of intensive securitization, and referred to the roles of DJI and DV&O staff as important partners in “basically everything what we do” (DTenV regievoerder 1). For example, the DJI Medewerker Vreemdelingenzaken has a first conversation with migrants upon entrance, which is for DTenV a first indication how much willingness to return is expressed by the migrant in question. Also, in detention setting, DTenV regievoorders have regular meetings with health-related experts as mental wellbeing of detained migrants is heavily under pressure, and at times closely surveilled. For the Rotterdam Detention center, one brigade of the Royal Police is geographically close by, which facilitates efficient legal transition in case the situation asks for it. As our respondents explained, when lawyers start a renewed asylum procedure for a detained migrant, the legal ground for detention needs to be changed. Then the migrant stays within the detention center, and the Royal Police comes in to talk to the person and change the legal ground for his detention. As indicated with some examples throughout the report, the DTenV regievoorders working in the detention center align with IOM officers. While migrant networks and local communities are not so much present in these settings, there are a few advocacy groups that monitor detention processes closely.

Next to these external relations, we have seen in this report how some DTenV regievoorders referred to the internal dynamics making their work more difficult, as in the example of bureaucratic and monitoring pressures from higher levels. We also heard how frictions may emerge between state actors of the ‘vreemdelingenketen’. The deviating viewpoints between COA and DTenV regarding the right to asylum accommodation is one case in point, see Section 5.2. Or we have seen how administrative mistakes of IND trickle down to DTenV (in)activities, such as in the case a box in the system is not checked off, while it is necessary to make the deportability of a person visible. For these cases, the IND representatives acknowledged that mistakes can be made, and that at times the INDIGO software system they use “may not correctly generate” the legal entitlements. At the same time, the same IND representatives we met claim that DTenV regievoorders should know that they are very approachable, and that they can always check with IND staff whenever something appears to be wrong (IND Representative 1 and 2). They also refer to the improvements made in this matter since 2015, as discussed above. In a formal reaction to this report, the DTenV states that “in general the registration of these titles is correct.”

Box 6: The Europeanization of return I

So far this report has pictured the Dutch RMI as a national entity. In reality, the European Union also plays an important role in how returns are put in practice. This is for instance clear from the

increasing role of Frontex in return migration governance (see also Chapter 6). There are charter flights coordinated on a European level (Walters 2024), and coordinating these charters requires quite some administrative labour (see Backman 2024 for further details), and these operations may fail on legal details. This is illustrated by DTenV regievoorders remembering a charter flight to Nigeria that was organized in the time of the Covid pandemic:

We had some charter flights to Nigeria during the Covid period, and we were all quite mad here, because this charter flight was arranged by DTenV (higher level) in the framework of Frontex in order to deport Nigerians during the Covid period. And we all said beforehand, this is about to fail, because it was not prepared properly. And on the work floor, you notice the unrest it creates. You also notice – well this is not correctly prepared, they did not think of this aspect, this is not agreed upon, and this is not right. And here, around this table, we have quite some knowledge [about the operations of return flights], and *we all agree that this is about to fail*, but *STILL* we need to put this family in detention! [with a loud voice]. In this case, luckily, just before detention, the flight was cancelled.

Interviewer: That is lucky indeed

Yes, that might be the case, but the labour involved! That is considerable. And the stress involved! Also for us, because in the end, we are humans too.

Like in the beginning of this year, there was again such charter flight. And I had six families that were ‘a possibility’ for these flights. Administratively, it is a drama, because it is a lot of work, because you need to fill out this information for three different people in three different forms, and if you forget to tick the right box, then it won’t happen, then it is thrown back to you. Really a drama. In the end, the list of six families shrunk to four families, and I believe in the end none of them have departed.

And the plane is there?

Yes or no, it depends, But there is a lot of pressure coming from the Hague, because the Netherlands buys airplane seats from Frontex, and these are not just seats for migrants and their children, but also for the staff supervising them. Escorts accompany them, so there is a lot of money involved, and hence the pressure from higher level. There are lists, and you are monitored, and then you are told that you did not do this or that. That is the stress. While *we know beforehand*, this is not going to happen. (DTenV regievoorder 4 and 5)

Next to these coordinated charter flights, Frontex (the European border agency) is a relatively new player in offering assisted return options. Most of the DTenV regievoorders we talked with, have not effectively made use of this programme called EURP (formerly known as JRS). Some stated to “work on it” and “to test it” (DTenV regievoorder 3), others shared some firm criticism :

Well it is the third time they changed the name. Look, I work for such a long time in the migration chain, and European collaboration has been discussed for such a long time. When I worked in Ter Apel, the only collaboration I have seen as that every member state of the European Union came to us to see how we deal with the situation, and then they leave, and that is basically it. And now they invented EURP, for me it is a monster [“gedrocht”]. It is MEGA, and not easy. Everything has to be communicated in English, well you have to be capable in terms of language, it is vague too (DTenV regievoorder 4)

According to this respondent, assisted return options are much easier arranged by involving IOM. From the setting of detention, however, EURP/JRS is effectively used. Migrants may then more easily shift from a forced removal without reintegration assistance to this programme that has some financial gains, as DTenV regievoorder 1 outlined in reference to returns to Morocco:

Then they switch, in the sense that they realize when I reach that point, I can better collaborate. And then JRS is a good option, then they receive reintegration assistance with a monetary value of 2000 euro, and in addition there is 615 euro they can claim, and mostly they prefer

this in cash when they arrive in Morocco, they can collect the money within 10 days. ... For me this programme is a more human way of returning people [in comparison to forced removal], and that is the way to go. Now, finally, we have this tool to work with. But of course they can still opt for IOM.

Finally, a form of Europeanization of return governance is through training programmes in return and reintegration counselling (RRC training programme). DTenV regievoorders may follow European trainings elsewhere, or may assist other teams elsewhere in Europe. Regievoorder 1 outlined this by saying:

Colleagues of me are sent to different countries quite regularly to train other colleagues on 'motivating techniques for return conversations', to train them with the latest insights, and to show them the best practices. In Bulgaria, for instance, our work [return conversations] is done by regular police officers. In that sense, the DTenV is quite an extraordinary organization. In Slovenia, police officers do the work as well. They form teams that still have quite some development to go ["moeten nog een ontwikkelingslag maken"]. DTenV also sent their staff to this RRC training, the return and reintegration counseling training, that is a club of trainers composed by some Dutch, Swedish, Austrian return officers, and they are much more advanced in these terms, they want to share their experience with colleagues .. These countries can request these trainings under the umbrella of Frontex. Under this same umbrella, people of our team go to Cyprus or Italy, but mainly Cyprus, to support local border guards with the inflow of asylum seekers and migrants.

5.5. Concluding notes

This Chapter has analyzed return migration infrastructures, primarily from the perspective of DTenV regievoorders working on returns in asylum settings or detention settings. It analyzed the roles and doings of these actors, and related these practices to the wider web of relations. The vreemdelingenketen is at the heart of a rather stringent post-arrival enforcement regime (Leerkes and Van Houte 2020). In their local practices, information is often bounded and fragmented, and DTenV regievoorders 'bricolage' fragments of information for their file-making. This counts for formal platforms like the LKO and identity-related research, but we also came across very informal ways of information sharing. Strong, and at times surprising, coalitions emerge based on proximity (e.g. IOM and DTenV in detention or Vluchtelingenwerk and DTenV in asylum locations), or interpersonal relations. As the DTenV is located in the middle of multifold relations, they are not the only actor that matter in return migration governance. From the political level of diplomacy to more on the ground realities of legal spaces to manoeuvre and resistant agency of migrants, DTenV regievoorders are confronted with considerable levels of dependency. Through their intercultural expertise, their experiences, creativity, persistence and autonomy, they constantly seek to stay in control, while they themselves also seem to realize that this control is always relative as decisions, acts or reluctance of others impact their work. Switching gears in terms of scenarios, coercion or partnerships are then often seen operational responses to these dependencies. Next to this, time management, including forecasting/anticipations and accelerations (e.g. Cleton 2022), are inherent aspects of the operational practices as well. This counts for the daily doings of DTenV regievoorders, but also the Dutch RMI at large. This is for example illustrated by the way DTenV regievoorders touched upon the 'geopolitical momentum of forced removals' of Moroccan nationals.

In the next Chapter, we further de-centre the analysis of RMIs in the Netherlands by paying explicit attention to the roles of NGOs in the particular framework of the LVV programme.

6. Infrastructuring Assisted Return?: Landelijke Vreemdelingen Voorziening (LVV)

The LVV is the Dutch national pilot project offering supervision and shelter to undocumented migrants in five cities: Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Utrecht, Eindhoven and Groningen. The formalized objective of the LVV is to find sustainable solutions for irregular migrants. In the national programme there have been three solutions identified: assisted return, onward migration and regularized stay. As stated before, the LVVs in the five cities have many commonalities, but they should not be considered a homogeneous space as local constellations, rules and capacities vary considerably. In this chapter, we follow a decentered approach and focus on the **roles, doings, materialities & technologies and relations** of LVVs, mainly from the perspective of NGOs attached to this programme.

6.1. Infrastructuring Assisted Return: Positioning NGOs and their Roles in LVV

The LVV programme was partly designed to promote better collaborations between governmental bodies (DTenV, IND and AVIM) and municipalities to manage undocumented migrants.⁷¹ While the formal arrangement was made between national and local government levels, it soon involved particular NGOs working in the field of migration. The NGOs involved does not include the International Organization for Migration (IOM), but we do discuss the role of this international actor in Textbox 7.

The LVV programme has been coordinated on a national level by the so-called programmabureau, but there is also a strong local articulation of governance for the involvement of local municipalities (*gemeentes*). State actors have mainly a monitoring and assisting role in the programme, as one IND representative indicated “our role is to think along” [meedenken en meekijken] (IND Representative 1) (see also De Haan 2024; Mack et al 2022).

The municipalities pay the NGOs that offer shelter. The funding consists of an amount that is calculated per individual per day and it adds up for the number of days the migrant stays in the LVV. In addition, NGOs, especially those assisting returns, rely on additional subsidies, most notably the Ondersteuning Zelfstandig Vertrek subsidy of DTenV. In addition, some NGOs found funding in, among others, the European AMIF funds or through private and more collective donations.

In terms of the NGOs involved, we may distinguish three roles of NGOs.

1. Offering shelter to undocumented migrants enrolled in the LVV programme,
2. Offering return assistance and reintegration support, and;
3. Providing legal support.

⁷¹ The basis of the LVV was a covenant between the national government and the VNG. In addition, each locally embedded LVV location had its one separate covenant.

While many NGOs play one of these roles outlined, some are characterized by a multiplicity of roles. There are locations with organisations providing legal assistance, future counselling, shelter *as well as* return counselling. In another location, the same roles are more divided between actors. For this report, we primarily focus on the first two roles.

Whatever their exact roles are, the daily realities of NGOs are filled with dilemmas as they “have manoeuvred themselves into the ambiguous position of simultaneously advocating the interests of migrants and serving the government by acting as a loyal player within the immigration system” (Kox and Staring 2022, p. 976; see also Merlin Escorza et al. 2021). From this position, certain discrepancies and frictions have become an inherent part in the LVV programme. This becomes particularly clear in terms of formulating priorities and objectives. Although all the actors – state and non-state actors – present in the LVV support the general objective of the programme (finding sustainable solutions for people without the right to stay), there are considerable discrepancies regarding the question on what to put priorities. From the perspective of the immigration authorities, the prioritized sustainable solution of this programme is (assisted) return, and only if this cannot be achieved, regularization is considered to be a welcome alternative (Mack et al. 2022). One IND representative stated the following in relation to this prioritization:

The secretary of state agreed with the local aldermen to prioritize returns – and the IND tried to take all the ‘edges off’ [‘de scherpe randjes er af te halen’]. Meaning, not trying endlessly to start a fourth of fifth repeated asylum claim, but *first* look at return as an option (Interview IND representative 1).

In contrast, for some of the NGOs talking about returns without re-exploring legal solutions would not work in the first place, as one NGO representative stated:

[In this city], we made very clear that the wishes of participants matter. Participation is a rather ambiguous concept, of course. But if people approach us with the question whether we can explore any legal opportunities to stay here...Could this be explored *one more time please?* Then it is madness if you don’t take this opportunity because the eventual next step [return counselling] won’t work either. Only with this first step [of re-exploring legal options], you can finally conclude, no sorry, there is nothing we can do to let you stay here. So, from this point of view, it is important to first check carefully, are all legal means *really* exhausted (LVV related NGO 1).

Another representative in a different city emphasized a similar logic by saying:

We're not working with a time limit or something, how long a person can stay, but what's leading for us is the commitment from the person, the motivation from the person to change the situation where he or she is in right now and like the guiding that we give ... We don't think that just giving a time limit is a solution

And he/she continued:

They all got a negative before, they all been in the process before they all had conversations with the DTenV before they all heard that they had to leave the country, that they were not getting a permit. Yeah, but they didn't go. What the situation is they're still in the Netherlands and they didn't go back. And they ask our help and most of the time it's not the help: can you please help me return? But the help is: please they didn't look at my story very well. I have not been treated honestly and things like that. I need

help because I will be in danger if I go back. So for us, it's not helping if we say now you got the negative, let's talk about the return (LVV related NGO 4).

The latest numbers of the LVV monitor (August 2024) indicate that the NGOs have a good reason to insist on legal (re-)explorations, as 445 people have been regularized through the LVV programme, which is actually a higher number than the 208 people that have been returned through these programmes (Ministerie van Veiligheid en Justitie n.d.; Interview Municipal Project Leader; Interview NGO). Some partners in the LVV talked proudly how a large share of their HASAs or a considerable share of health-related cases have led to regularization.⁷² For the IND, this legal space to manoeuvre is seen as counterproductive as it basically prevents people from working actively on their return in the first place. As an IND representative stated:

The NGOs may say that it [the programme] works, but actually the results are... Not so fantastic. We have 200 people who have returned with the LVV, let's be honest.

...

What we don't know, well we know that preparations are being made for LHGTBQ and religious converts ["bekerigen"], and that discussions are taking place there – or courses, whatever you want to call it – but *how* that takes place, *what happens there*, we as IND actually don't know. There is no transparency about that. But we do see that it in the end leads to a higher acceptance rates, with HASAs that are well prepared and with people who know how to formulate it [IND Representative 1].⁷³

The second IND representative made this unease even more explicit in the same interview, by saying:

I've managed to build quite a good relationship with them [the NGOs]. So I'm pretty good at working together. I do notice that they are very much [focusing] on residence instead of return – that is my irritation. Then I'm thinking 'hello?! we also have to look at return'. That is the intention [IND Representative 2].

Based on the different prioritizations in the LVV by NGOs, a new proposal from the Dutch Ministry of Security and Justice is developed to further reduce the legal space to manoeuvre for participants of the LVV programme. This proposal is called the Two Phases Model and was actually implemented in 2024. This model takes three months period for a so-called perspective determination, with “return and regularization as two equal perspectives” [“terugkeer en verblijf als gelijkwaardig perspectief”] (IND Representative 1; NGO related to LVV 1). If there are no grounds to question a previous return decision, then the model insists on a full focus on return. The main difference is that with the new model reduces considerably

⁷² Some representatives claimed that the share of HASAs that have been granted reached 80% or even 96%.

⁷³ Interestingly, one of the coordinators of municipality also referred to the cases of LHGTBQ and religious converts, but with a different standpoint stressing the complexity of proving it: “For example, if you are LGBT or becoming Christian. How do you prove that? We can say, yeah, we have I don't know, five pastors stories of a reference to saying, yeah. Yeah. He goes to church every week. But is that enough proof? And then the IND said no, he has to Consistently Declare about the way his belief is growing. If you ask me how I do that if I would be Christian or I'm from Catholic descent, I have no idea about what to say. So there, they will see how difficult it can be. Because if the person doesn't know what is expected and the IND is also in a grey area, then it's difficult” (Local coordinator LVV municipality 1)

the time period for the legal trajectory (from 18 to 3 months), narrowing the chances for regularisations.

Our interviews indicated how state agencies do urge to work on return more effectively in the LVV setting. For instance, we were told how the DTenV proposed that migrants could only enter the LVV programme when they have spent a year ‘on the streets’, an idea that is strongly contested by local coordinators (Interview Local Coordinator Municipality 1). Other DTenV suggestions for more effectivity on return, however, do have a concrete result:

I know that the DTenV wants us to do more. And of course, we're also talking about how we can do that more without frustrating our relationship with the client, with the person, so we're also talking about that and to see what..., so we make a kind of agreement also that for people whereby the identity or nationality is not known, the team is also going to have conversations with them on identity and nationality, for getting a legal stay, for returning, for all situations. ... So we're working more together in this kind of cases [NGO involved in LVV 4].

This interview suggests that even in on one of the most important bottlenecks for forced removals – the identity confirmation – NGOs may play an important indirect role in terms of identification and information sharing. In other words, NGOs might not explicitly collaborate with state actors on forced removals, they might even openly contest them, but through these small acts they indirectly smoothen these processes at the same time. NGOs can indeed be a facilitating and contesting actor of forced return migration at the very same time (Merlin Escorza et al. 2021). It is fair to state, however, that we also came across cases whereby NGOs contested identity determination of the IND in rather persistent ways.

In terms of defining roles, particular attention should be given to the position of NGOs that offer return assistance from the LVV programme. For the NGOs offering return assistance, the LVV is an important, but not the only ground to work from. The respective representatives we spoke to presented cases of spontaneous return, referred to recruitment and advertisement activities at COA locations, or explained how IOM or DTenV transfers cases to them. When asking about the role in LVV, these NGOs providing return assistance described it in line with the following formulations:

The main aim of our organizations is to provide tailor-made services. When it comes to someone who wants to return, a country of origin and that that can be done in a sustainable way [NGO offering return assistance 3].

To unpack this tailor-made service a bit further, it is relevant to note that LVV programmes collaborate with particular pre-selected NGOs that offer return assistance, except from the city of Groningen where return trajectories are more directly monitored by DTenV regievoorders. When a migrant follows a return trajectory, the specific NGOs are matched with migrants in the LVV based on country-specific expertise, partnerships and track-record in particular countries. In this respect, we often heard the term ‘landenlijstje’ [list of countries]. For instance, the programme offered by Vluchtelingenwerk called Met Opgeheven Hoofd (With Head Up High) only offers return assistance to people who are moving to a country that is considered to be safe (as their entire vision is based on refugee protection), while Goedwerk Foundation also works in countries that are seen as unsafe. For this particular profile, the latter actor, receives quite some critique, not only from some of our interview partners, but

also more publicly.⁷⁴ As a response to this critique, representatives of Goedwerk Foundation stressed the autonomy of return decisions as the following interview fragment discloses:

Interviewer: Perhaps a more sensitive question. When it comes to the choice of country within your expertise, people sometimes say to us: 'I would never send someone back to Eritrea, because Eritrea is a country you shouldn't send someone back to' ... Why did you choose to do so in the first place, what is the motivation for that?

It is a topic of conversation [in our organization]. The main thing we think when it comes to people who have a return wish is that they make it themselves. People decide for themselves that they want to return, and the moment we think it can be done in a sustainable way, who are we to say it cannot be done? Of course, we always take the situation into account. For example, we have a partner in Afghanistan. The situation in Afghanistan, we all know, is not good right now. But people make that choice themselves and the moment we can facilitate them in that, then we are behind it.

Regardless the question of how much pressure is involved in return assistance to unsafe countries, the involvement of this NGO shows that - from the state's perspective - the LVVs include NGOs that clearly compliment each other in terms of geographical coverage, partnerships and 'services' they offer. Moreover, it discloses how these state-NGO constructions create overlapping responsibilities that hamper accountability of the state (e.g. Schapendonk 2018). As legal scholar dr. Carolus Grütter put it in a newspaper article (NRC 2024b): "The principle of the rule of law [het principe van de rechtstaat] is that the government is transparent and accountable. This is not the case in this construction. What Goedwerk promises to migrants – in the name of the government – remains unclear. When something goes wrong, we know nothing. Then, no-one is accountable."⁷⁵

Box 7: The role of the IOM in the RMI

Although the IOM is not directly involved in LVV programme⁷⁶, this well-known international organization can be considered the main provider of return and reintegration assistance (AVRR) for returnees from the Netherlands since 1992. IOM provides return counselling themselves, but they are crucial for NGOs for their assistance in obtaining travel documents from the diplomatic representations, flight booking, monetary and in-kind assistance as well as reintegration assistance in the countries of origin. In addition, the IOM provides operational escorting to returnees with medical issues or in vulnerable situations such as women with children, where they accompany the returnees in their return journey starting in Schiphol through the customs, migration authorities, the KMar, on the airplane and till they pass the customs at the country of return where the local IOM staff take over. In describing their role in the RMI, IOM officers stressed the power of being a global player in the field of return or the fact that they have access to all COA locations and are present in

⁷⁴ See NRC newspaper article: [Uitgeprocedeerd? Deze NGO Beloofd Je Duizenden Euro's Als Je Vertrekt, Uitgeprocedeerd? Deze ngo belooft je duizenden euro's als je vertrekt - NRC](#), accessed on 8-10-2024

⁷⁵ Dutch translation: "Het uitgangspunt van de rechtsstaat is dat de overheid transparant te werk gaat en daarop zelf aanspreekbaar is. Dat is in deze opzet niet het geval. Wat Goedwerk allemaal namens de overheid belooft aan de migrant, valt niet na te gaan. En als het misgaat, weten we van niets. Dan is er niemand meer op aan te spreken." See NRC newspaper article: [Uitgeprocedeerd? Deze NGO Beloofd Je Duizenden Euro's Als Je Vertrekt, Uitgeprocedeerd? Deze ngo belooft je duizenden euro's als je vertrekt - NRC](#), accessed on 8-10-2024.

⁷⁶ However, we were told that the IOM funds ten beds in the LVV-related locations in the city of Amsterdam.

detention facilities.⁷⁷ Consequently, many smaller parties in the field, rely on IOM's networks, operational services and expertise. A few NGO representatives also questioned the rather central role of IOM, as NGO Return Assistance 1 stated:

Sometimes it feels that referring people to other organisations is easier than keeping them inside our organisation. ... I sometimes see how people *per default* are sent to IOM, and this used to be the route indeed, but today we can offer so much tailor-made work for them. That is a real shame, actually. ... I think we can offer better services, particularly to the most vulnerable people.

On the other hand, several IOM representatives expressed some scepticism regarding the mushrooming of return programmes in the Netherlands, as they seldom saw the value added of these programmes. All in all, there seems to exist a 'we do it better' mentality at both the side of the IOM as well as the NGOs. This mentality is reflected in claims like:

My colleague is much more effective than IOM or DTenV when it concerns obtaining the right documents. For instance, in case a small paper needs to be added from a school or church in a little village somewhere, *she really makes this happen*" (NGO Return Assistance 1)

We have everything in our hands ... [The NGOs offering return assistance], I don't see any added value. Not really no, they are small and do things. To be honest, I don't see their added value (IOM Officer 1)

The problems emerge between NGOs. There is a kind of battle like 'I am the best, no I am the best' ... Return organisations, in Amsterdam, Rotterdam and elsewhere, I sense a tension between them. Like 'this is *ours*, and you should not do that' ... It is like protecting their own territory [NGO Return Assistance 2]

We know how to find IOM. But the thing with IOM is uhm, IOM can arrange voluntary return, but ... the mindset should already be on returning [NGO related to LVV 4].

6.2. Doings

For the various roles of NGOs in the LVV there are particular phased doings. For the NGOs providing shelters, we may distinguish administrative work (intake/screening, reporting), care work, operational work (such as arranging housing) and lobbying work. For NGOs that primarily provide return assistance, we came across a variety of activities including return counselling, providing information to other 'ketenpartners', providing future orientation programs, advisory sessions with (groups of) possible returnees, assisting with document procurement, facilitating contact with embassies and consulates, arranging and maintaining partnerships in the countries of origin, enabling financial resources to support return, arranging flights (in collaboration with IOM and DTenV) and participating in meetings with other organisations. Below, we seek to unpack particular *doings* by following the general temporal logic of returns within the LVV programme: from intake, future counselling, return trajectory, the actual return and administrative justification.

⁷⁷ One respondent indicated how upon first entrance in the pre-removal detention center migrants are immediately confronted with the IOM's presence: "They enter, and they wait in a 'wachtsel", and there the visibility of IOM begins with posters.

The first step of an LVV programme concerns an intake and screening. In most cases NGOs arrange this intake in a space that feels relatively safe for migrants (e.g. a community center or particular desk for undocumented people). One interviewee responsible for this process outlined the following:

So we start with some first checks to see if they meet the criteria here. Because we do have some regulations here, we cannot help everybody. If for instance, people have no ties with Amsterdam, they cannot stay here. If they have Dublin, they cannot stay here. So we do the IND check, to see if there is no criminal offence, or to see if there is no Dublin claim. Then we prepare a case for LSO. The LSO decides whether to place somebody in LVV programmes or not.

And I also heard that AVIM is involved, how would that work?

Yes, the AVIM is the very first step. They register there. ... They take fingerprints, photos and they [migrants] enter it in the system. They also check whether there have no crimes been committed in the past. They don't do it here, in this building. We send the clients over there, and so they'll go there independently. At first they proposed to do these check-ins of the AVIM here in the same place, but If AVIM would do it here, it would change the atmosphere completely"

Yes, but I can imagine people are also hesitant because they might be fearful.

Yes for this step there is a lot of fear. But then I try to call them and tell them this step is really necessary for the process. They are not running a risk of forced return with this step, it is a moment to get access to the programme. Most of the time I can comfort them and convince them they should do it (Interview LVV related NGO 2).

In this setting, it is clear that the NGO finds itself in a balancing act of, on the one hand, clearly securing an autonomous space by *not* doing the AVIM intakes in their locations, while on the other hand still convincing migrants to register at the AVIM. Some of the NGOs stressed in the interview that providing a safe zone for undocumented people is an important condition for their work. At the same time, the above procedures around the intake resemble, and align well with, similar registration practices of migration apparatuses (see also Merlin Escorza et al. 2021; Kalir and Wissink 2016).

After the intake, a migrant file is sent to the LSO – the platform from where LVVs are locally managed – or is reviewed by the coordinating civil servant of the municipality. The LSO or civil servant decides upon the question whether someone can be admitted to the LVV programme and which trajectory this person should follow: legal trajectory, future orientation, return counselling. Based on the trajectory, the migrant is linked to a case manager (can be a legal expert, future counselling, or return). In some settings, the LVV makes use of *casus regisseurs* and *case managers*. The difference is that the *regisseur* is monitoring several cases that are basically in the hands of the case managers.

Interestingly, in terms of the guidance of NGOs of people without the right to stay in the enrollment of the programme there is a parallel between NGOs and state actors like the DTenV regievoorders and COA case managers. Both state and non-state actors stress the importance of the building of trust *as well as* starting from a particular form of 'honesty' or 'directness' to migrants. The trust relationship with migrants is articulated by all NGOs we spoke to, and it is seen as a characteristic that distinguishes them from DTenV (and to a lesser extent IOM).

With trust, so they reason, they try to break with stigma and fear around returns (NGO return assistance 2). Directness and confrontation, however, are also part of the storyline, as one representative of an NGO in the LVV commented:

It's important that it can be on a base of trust with somebody and that it's voluntary, but we will be honest with people, what are the possibilities and what's not possible, and then of course, we always say it's his or her life and we are here to help, to guide the person and that didn't change with the LVV's coming for us [Interview NGO related to LVV 4].

NGOs offering return assistance become more relevant when the LSO directs a case to future counselling. Future counselling is more than only return conversations, but return is an inherent component of these conversations with people who have not yet decided upon their plans (NGO Return Assistance 2). The moment the migrant has openly opted to return can be seen as “het omklapmoment” (NGO return assistance 2) from where future counselling is turning into a return trajectory. NGOs offering return assistance then constantly monitor ‘where the migrant is in the process’, have further in-depth conversations with migrants, and provide future training programmes, mainly around business development. Only in very exceptional cases, return trajectories are switched back to legal trajectories.⁷⁸

Next to these migrant-related doings, NGO workers in the field of return basically do the things DTenV regievoorders are doing in terms of organizing the practicalities of returns. Interestingly, like in the case of DTenV regievoorders, many NGOs representatives outlined how they consider themselves a central player in all the relational work involved: i.e. obtaining the needed documents from diplomatic representations, advising (or asking advise of) colleagues, verifying with the DTenV whether a migrant is eligible to receive return assistance; or contacting the IND when, for instance, it holds the migrant’s passport; calling the IOM which provides the REAN assistance for flight booking and travel compensation; checking with partners about departure and return details; or assisting in cases with particular medical conditions. There is a special role for the local counterparts of NGOs, working in the countries of origin. In a rather early stage, NGOs actually invite their local counterparts in the countries of origin to explain from their side to the ‘client’ how return processes unfold. Involving the counterpart in the process, as we noticed, is not only about sharing information, but actually to win more trust from the migrant and to *ease* the migrant in this process.⁷⁹ These counterparts vary from being formalized organisations in the ESRO network (in the case of Vluchtelingenwerk for instance), to rather individuals who serve as rather informal contacts in some cases (see also Section 6.4).

Next to these commonalities between the NGOs’ doings, there was one particular activity that some NGOs practiced more than others: stretching of financial support in return processes. Several NGOs stressed how they work in-between the financial lines of standard assisted return support of the IOM: €1800. The to-be-returned migrant receives a bounded sum of

⁷⁸ We came across one example of a man in the return trajectory, but at a certain point in time the a man declared that a return was out of the question, because his son was kidnapped a few days ago. This brought new legal grounds for a repeated asylum claim (HASA).

⁷⁹ In the interview with a return NGO that returns people to countries that are considered to be *unsafe*, it was formulated as follows: “What we do, when people consider to return to a country like Syria, we call our partner, and we call previously returned migrants. Not to push them, but to show them like hey now you can listen to stories of people who have actually returned.”

cash, and the rest is transferred to a counterpart organisation in the country of origin. The migrant then may access these funds to buy materials that support their reintegration process. Several partners – including the DTenV – suggested that this amount of money is often insufficient to convince a migrant to return.⁸⁰ Hence, some actors actively seek ways to strengthen this financial incentive. One way of doing this is by adding financial support from own funds, which is not only done by the more entrepreneurial NGO we spoke to. Other ways of doing is to seek matching funds from municipalities (usually €500), as some cities created budgets to boost the funding of return processes.⁸¹ On the question, whether funds are matched, NGO Return Assistance 2 responded:

There are indeed add-ups, coming from DTenV or the municipality. When somebody has a really nice project, you may search for some extra money.

Another NGO representative delved into this issue with more detail:

There is a standard contribution of 200 euro by the IOM, they get it on the airport, and the rest?! Well that depends on the commitment and persuasiveness of our colleagues, to contact the municipality or the DTenV and ask for extra financial means. This happens quite often, depending on the local manager or DTenV regievoerder. Some will be willing to pay more, and give us 500 euro extra, others might say, no sorry. It also depends on the situation. ... In Amsterdam there is now the financial construction that on the moment you submit an extraordinary departure case, and the DTenV grants this submission, the local municipality automatically matches this [with €500]. That is a really nice construction. But basically, our approach is, you can always try and ask for more, “niet geschoten is altijd mis.” ... Look, one of the things we see quite often is that people want to start a taxi business upon return. And for €1000 I can easily buy a car in a country like Algeria (NGO Return Assistance 3).⁸²

Earlier in the same interview, we discussed how migrants are informing each other about differences and possibilities, and the respondents emphasized that this kind of financial information is easily shared among migrants.

On the day of departure, many NGO workers assist the migrants until the IOM desk at Schiphol Airport. There the migrant is transferred to the IOM staff. This transfer is not without frictions, we heard. According to some NGO representatives, the IOM desk can be rather stringent. One respondent complained:

For some IOM workers, we cannot even stand behind their desk. We need to wait at the other side. Come on! We are the trust person [‘vertrouwenspersoon’]. *You* don’t know

⁸⁰ €1800 euros is generally considered to be low as financial support. DTenV regievoerder 3 stated: “Yesterday, I had a conversation with a Nigerian man, he simply laughed at me, and said, I cannot do anything with that money.” The position of the Nigerian man suggests that there is still space for negotiation in migrant-DTenV encounters (Schapendonk 2018). To return families, the financial incentivization is more substantial as you “can request €2000 per family member. So, for example, in case there are many kids, then it easily reaches €10,000” (referring to EURP / Frontex option)

⁸¹ We heard about at least Eindhoven and Amsterdam.

⁸² There are exceptional cases where the stretching of funding go well beyond the €500/1000 range. In the NRC (2024b) article, one to-be-returned migrant speaks of a compensation up to €20.000. It is also acknowledged that the financial options widen considerably in cases of people who are considered to be a concrete burden for society [‘overlastgevers’].

him. Just give us the possibility. People are nervous to return, do you understand? In my view, you need to give us the opportunity to accompany the migrant further in the process. Some IOM officers are really static. ‘No, we cannot allow you.’ You cannot chase us [the NGO workers] away like that. These are really annoying situations.

In this setting after the border control at the airport, the only pre-departure care that is possible for NGOs is a phone call when the to-be-returned migrant has passed the KMar check and waits at the gate to embark the airplane. In exceptional cases, however, NGOs also provide ‘social escorts’, which indeed implies that they travel with the person to a particular place.

When the migrant is returned, the doings of NGO workers does not stop, it is actually the start of a lot of administrative work. Thus, the paperwork involved does not only *mobilize* returns (e.g. subscription in the programme, collecting the paper work, documenting a file), it is also about *justifying* the financial spendings. Or is one interviewee indicated: “from the moment somebody has returned, the administrative maze [rompslomp] starts.”

In this justification of the costs made, the local partner in the country of origin plays a crucial role, as the representative of NGO Return Assistance 1 outlines:

Partners often accompany the migrant. In any case, for Nigeria, the client shops *hand in hand* with the partner and arranges everything. For example, to obtain a rental agreement [huurcontract], or driver’s license, this all costs money. They cannot spend it like this, nooo, we need to get the receipts. And, from my own experience I know that not every country is accustomed to providing receipts. So that is super complicated (Interview NGO Return Assistance 1).

With a sense of joyful irritation, this interviewee shared more details about the challenge of financial accountability:

Well....that is the beginning of the *real* administration [started to laugh]. Because every expense, need to come with a receipt, and this receipt needs to be linked to the client, *preferably with a signature*. This is enormous work. ... Now we have to report to the DTenV, it used to be AMIF for us, that is a European programme. So the ‘bonnetjescontrole’, you know what I am talking about, is a tiny bit easier with the DTenV, but their accountant, they may open an entire file at the end of a project, and *every* receipt should be in order.

Finally, there are activities of these NGOs regarding post-return evaluations. This may include phone calls to returnees or phone calls to partners. Some organisations have agreed with their local partners that they monitor the returnee for a period of a year. They then send monitoring reports to the Dutch side of the RMI. Others stated to monitor the returns themselves, partly based on field visits. They report the reintegration progress in reports. These rather elaborative reports were basically seen as “information provision to the ketenpartners.” Understandably, NGO representatives expressed a satisfied feeling in cases of successful returns, i.e. when people manage to get back on their feet again. Occasionally, it happens that former ‘clients’ are in the end unhappy with the return (and the process of return itself). Very few interviewees touched upon this, one notable exception is NGO Return Assistance 4, who stated:

We had a case of a family, coming here with their passports, and saying, we really want to go back. But once they arrived there, feelings of regret started to emerge. It did not go well. That is a confrontation with ourselves. Sometimes – and this is the other side of

the coin, returns do not work well. You have to be aware of that, and ask yourself, how far do we go? That is a confrontation with ourself (NGO Return Assistance 4)

The 'how far do you go' question raised above is particularly interesting for its reflexivity. The question, of course, is to what extent this reflexivity leads to the actual changing of practices.

6.3. Materials & technologies

To discuss the material dimension in this Chapter it is important to acknowledge the infrastructural challenge of finding appropriate accommodation in the LVV programme. After all, within the framework of this programme these shelters are important holding places for to-be-returned migrants. These shelters rely on invisible words of depots, volunteers transporting furniture, concierges, handymen, medical assistance, and so on. We heard how so-called woonbegeleiders [residential counsellors] constantly “*hustle*” and find creative solutions to make these accommodation liveable spaces. In the default situation, bedrooms and living spaces are shared among migrants. One of the physical characteristics of these shelter accommodations is that they often *do not stand out* in the neighbourhood. One NGO representative stated the following in this respect:” I don't think that the normal people living here that they know, that they are really aware, of the LVV” [NGO in LVV 4]. This was confirmed by a colleague in a different city:

It is sometimes funny, because oftentimes, in case of protest and unrest, people are concerned about undocumented migrants being located in their street, but oftentimes we receive questions like “when do these undocumented people actually arrive here” only three months *after* they have already been living there. Then I think, well there are already many people living there (NGO in LVV 1).

Next to the actual shelter locations, the materiality of the spaces of first encounter matter significantly. To illustrate this, we provide one example of our observations in the Textbox below.

Box 8: Materiality, trust and atmosphere

Materiality has a key role to play in atmosphere, as was also indicated in the example of the old and new hearing rooms of COA and DTenV (see Chapter 5). Through our ethnographic observations, we tend to show here how seemingly meaningless artefacts may have a story to tell. This is an example of an information desk for undocumented people, and the first entry to the LVV programme.

Prior to my appointment, I had some time to sense the room. A colourful place, with some signs of food preparation, breakfasts perhaps, a coffee corner with a machine, a kitchen, a small corner for young kids to spend their time playing with a tiny kitchen, cuddly toys and tools. Two large tables for conversations. It resembled a living space, shared collectively. Close to them on the ground floor, and above them, were the office spaces. In and around the living space there were a lot of signs about the caring for the case of undocumented people. Most notably a City Rights App, Migrant Rights advocacy posters, and these signs were often not far away from signs about sustainable futures and return. For its more intimate appearances the exposed drawings (made by kids), touched me. A colourful heart, a flower, as warm responses to the services unfolding in this location. Finally, two portraits in black and white caught my eye, near the toilets: “Raise a Paper Monument for the Paperless. Give a face to the Undocumented” It said in very tiny letters to let the face speak out. This place had a soul, so it felt.

The tour started with a remarkable tiny thing: a red ribbon that you can easily attach/detach to a pillar or wall – same ribbons that one sees in airports to demarcate the waiting lines. My interlocutor explained in words like: I usually start here, because when we came here with the programme this building looked very differently. ‘This ribbon was there like this’ [and she stretched the ribbon out to attach it to the other side of the entry in such a way that the ribbon says: ‘don’t enter’]. The interlocutor continued: “there was a clear separation between here, where the people waited, and there, where the people worked in front of screens, a very uncomfortable start. We wanted to change that, we wanted to create a more open and cozy space.” My interviewee continued by showing how the colours of the building changed (from very sterile to more warm colours) and explained that the office spaces were now moved to upstairs, while the downstairs offices were meant for conversations ‘inloopuren’ for migrants. I was shown the table for shared lunches. In all explanations, materiality mattered in terms of how trust with migrants in vulnerable positions is negotiated.

While this ethnographic impression is based on one location we visited, there are quite some parallels with other locations in terms of the presence of paper brochures about basic rights, legal possibilities, cities social map, psychological help for intersectional groups (LGBTQ and people of colour), places for free meals, etc.

In terms of technologies, we did not come across a wide variety of software systems, but in the LVV there were claims from different sides at the beginning of the programme that software should be developed. Monitoring the LVVs from simple excel sheets was undoable. Some respondents referred to Client Volgsysteem, others talked about Client Registratiesysteem, and again others stated to be very grateful for Microsoft Teams as the software supports LSO meetings.

6.4. Relations

When it comes to the internal relations of LVV, basically all actors (state *and* non-state) felt that the collaborations improved over years (Mack et al. 2022). However, friction is an inherent aspect of the pilot programme. This friction does not only emerge between state and non-state actors, but also emerge between governmental levels (state vs. municipalities). This multi-level governance friction was tellingly put by IND representative 1:

If they want, the local municipalities can truly build a beautiful programme or something that we – being the state – don’t like very much.⁸³

To focus on the relations that shape the daily operations of the LVV, we should start with the important platform called LSO: Lokale samenwerkingsoverleggen. These LSOs are mostly chaired by the local municipality, but there is no standardized frequency of LSO meetings. The LSO in Amsterdam occurs on a monthly basis, and in Rotterdam, Eindhoven and Groningen every two weeks. Although collaborations and atmospheres have improved in the LVV programme over years, some interviewees referred to the LVV programme as rather “fragile collaborations”. Nevertheless, many partners shared their positive evaluation of the LSO. To

⁸³ “Als ze willen, kan de lokale gemeente er wat moois van maken of iets wat wij – als Rijk zijnde – veel minder vinden.”

stress the positive interpretations here, one NGO involved in the LVV even called the LSO as meetings that are almost ‘frictionless’ (NGO in LVV 1) (see also De Haan 2024). A colleague elaborated on the relation with the DTenV:

Well I have been very critical for their work in detention, but here in this city the collaborations with DTenV works really well. We need them for many reasons, and they need us. Also because many people really want to go back. (NGO in LVV 2)

Like in the case of asylum locations (see Section 5.2), there are upscaling mechanisms in place when there is no agreement or solution found in the LSO. This upscaling happens often gradually, by first consulting steering committees of LVVs and ultimately the ‘Multidisciplinary Review Team’. This MRT team consists of senior state actors of the vreemdelingenketen and some non-state actors and together they look at the same case in order to prevent tunnel vision (NGO in LVV 1). In addition, the local LVV coordinators also have their own nation-wide meetings with each other, called projectleideroverleg. This facilitates a direct link to het Programmabureau at the national level.

One more sensitive point in the LVV relations is the sharing (and unsharing of information). Some NGOs in the LVV deliberately do not share *everything* with partners like the IND, as the following fragment of the interview with IND Representative 2 suggests.

At one point in time, I saw an email from one of our partners saying “yes the IND is involved too, but they should not know everything.” I acted immediately during our first meeting after this message, and I said [using a stringent tone]: Let me be frank, I have seen this email exchange, if this implies that some information is *not shared* with me, I am pulling out. And they reacted like ‘no no, this was not the intention’. OK, I replied, I want ALL information. I don’t want secrets for each other. And, after this, I think it is going quite well... I hope.

On their turn, NGOs have at times concerns regarding the implicit and explicit power relations involved. Although smooth LSO operations were mentioned by all actors, including NGOs, power seemed to be an inherent component of the LVV programme. This was for instance discussed above with the example of how the new proposal of two phases puts pressure on more effective and focused approaches on return in the LVV programme. Interestingly, one actor arranging the shelter saw a double-edged sword when it came to the question of power.

Of course there is a lot of power here. Most of the money is coming from DTenV, so if they decide in LSO we don’t want to place this person here, it will be very difficult for us. But it actually also works the other way around... for example, usually we don’t allow people with a heavy entry ban here in the LVV, a 10 year entry ban, but I have seen the way DT&V has used its power to actually bring him to the shelter. So it also works the other way around. [NGO in LVV Programme 2]

Building further on this power issue, the NGOs working on return tend to emphasize how they basically rely on the DTenV in terms of finance and operation. They are an “unavoidable partner”, as some respondent stated, and the fact that funding does come from them creates a form of “dependency” that includes audits (twice or three times a year). For the arrangements within the LVV programme the NGOs work on a basis of the previously mentioned “inspanningsverplichting”. For OZV subsidies is granted on project basis, meaning that organizations apply for funding in project cycles. In previous years, the project cycle was set

on three years, but since 2024 it is reduced to two years (NGO in LVV Programme 3). In this context, there are harsher targets at play. One respondent explained this with the following fragment on financial accountability:

What happens when the financial justification is not in order?

Then we are facing budget cuts.

From the DTenV?

Yes. And often, when there is something not right, they extrapolate this to all our cases. Like, if one is not right, then we assume a certain percentage of *all* the cases are not right, and as a consequence we receive less money. It is a stressful thing. (NGO Return Assistance 1).

One of the initiatives we interviewed indeed had to face budget cuts from the DTenV recently. This looming of cuts is also the reason why some organisations have a celebratory mood when a family is returned, as some respondent yelled: “yooo four people, four individuals at once!” These moments feel like “a victory”, she explained, as all four family members count in terms of reaching return targets.

In the practical operation of returns – i.e. booking flights, assisting to airport – there seems to be a shared preference amongst NGOs to collaborate with IOM to materialize a return. However, here there can be a continuum at play, as NGO Return Assistance 2 indicated:

So we usually collaborate with IOM, but there are cases like Turkey. We don't have a partner there, then we turn to IOM, but they could not book the ticket and could not obtain the travel papers, and then you go to DTenV, and they are able to arrange this, at least sometimes (NGO Return Assistance 2)

When contacting the DTenV, there may be reasons for caution for the NGOs as there is quite some incomplete information on how returns are actually administered.

I actually don't know how it exactly works, how it is registered, but somewhere it is stated that the person is returned by the DTenV. I believe you can also delete it, but somewhere it is stated that it concerns a forced removal, because DTenV has returned them. And I believe, you can do something about this [registration], but you have to actively act. And for the person in question, it does have real consequences. I should actually check how this actually works in practice, I in fact don't know.

This interview snapshot suggests that there is still a lot unknown about what the administrative consequences are when NGOs involve DTenV for their assistance. Another frustration of the same interviewee concerned the relentless attitude of some DTenV regiovoorders and she referred to cases of unnecessary detention, putting forward a gut feeling that detention is not always the ‘last resort’ as authorities present it to be.

Next to these NGO-state relations, there are many more relations that matter for the NGOs we spoke to. One of the most prominent connections are formed by the partnerships with organisations or individuals in the countries of origin. These relations are maintained by regular communication, but also occasionally by field trips of NGO workers. For some, an important condition is that the partner is *not working* with governmental bodies of a specific country, others stated that partner could actually be very helpful in getting the right documents from authorities.

While some partnerships run through larger frameworks such as the ESRO network of which Vluchtelingenwerk is an important member, one of the most important basis to collaborate with partners is 'knowing each other'. While this sounds self-evident for many formalized connections, it also creates space for more informal partnerships, including partnerships with entrepreneurial individuals. One NGO representative explained how she found partners through their personal networks, and often involve former clients. Self-evidently, this creates some convenience: "this personal bond makes collaborations smooth ... very low key." While informal relations might indeed make communication and agreements between partners and Dutch NGOs easier, that does not guarantee a productive professional relation for the to-be-returned migrants. A rather recent development is the Europeanization of partnership in the field of return migration, as discussed in Textbox 9 below.

Box 9: The Europeanization of Return II: Fear over relations: The Emergence Frontex' EURP/JRS programme

For the NGOs offering return assistance, the Europeanization of assisted returns through the EURP/JRS programme caused some significant shift, as state actors may in potential use this programme and take over the role these NGOs play. NGO representative narrated this risk in an illustrative way, by saying:

In practice, this [EURP] programme is not frequently used. We don't see it happen. One of the DTenV people I work with told me: 'yes we can also offer voluntary return now, but I don't know how it works', and I thought, OK that is fine, let it be this way, because we don't like it too much of course. Because we in the end offer these services, and we are sidelined if the programme is developing itself, then return counselling will be in the hands of the DTenV, that is not what we prefer (NGO Return Assistance 2).

Besides the DTenV taking over some of the tasks involved, other NGOs saw a risk in EURP as it straightjackets partnerships.

In the beginning we could just use our own partners, partners that we fully trust, but in the last 1,5 years or so, this is not allowed anymore. ... The Frontex/JRS programme, you are actually almost pushed into that – you almost have to make use of that. Well there are cases that we do want to make use of that, especially because in countries like Algeria and Morocco it is where it is difficult with partner networks.... Frontex, then again, can facilitate that. But you actually get a bit pressed there. It's also about having control, where before we actually always had it ourselves ... This is just, this is going to be a future failure. 100 per cent. Yes, absolutely. When I look at Ethiopia, Ghana, Uganda, what partners we have there, wonderful people with wonderful results. I can't imagine from those other networks, that we can expect the same. Absolutely not. It's static, just a distance.... And not only that, Frontex JRS is of course also a system where forced return is facilitated. Deportation. And that is something that we as an organization do not support.

Absolutely not ... So you also make a consideration like, hey, you do use a network that also facilitates that. You make this consideration because you consider it important to also serve the target group on which you have expertise.

Interestingly, this particular NGO, like the others we interviewed is trying to distance itself from the practices of forced removals, while they also receive direct funding from the DTenV and through this they have been incorporated in an RMI that is characterized by a continuum of coercion.

To finalize this section on relations, NGOs also feel responsible to a wider network or ecosystem of civil society organisations. The programmes of Vluchtelingenwerk are, for example, tied to a wider ecosystem of refugee protection. Hence, according to this logic, they cannot facilitate returns to areas that are considered unsafe. Another example of a wider ecosystem is the Gelagkameroverleggen in Amsterdam – a local platform for all kinds of NGOs and activist groups. NGOs working in the LVV setting are present in these platform meetings and they are quite frequently confronted with harsh criticism coming from more radical actors. In Groningen, Rotterdam and Utrecht LVV organisations have direct contact with progressive churches, like the Pauluskerk in Rotterdam or the INLIA network⁸⁴. These latter initiatives have a long history of contesting the exclusion of irregular migrants in general, and the return migration agenda of the Dutch state more specifically (e.g. Van den Broek 2024).

6.5. Concluding notes

This Chapter followed a de-centering approach to analyze return migration governance through the LVV programmes. From the beginning, the initial idea of the national government was to build in a firm conditionality in this pilot programme: migrants may only enter the shelters on the condition that they ‘work on their return’. However, through the ‘multilevel struggle’ between the state and city administrations – which has been an inherent characteristic of the Dutch migration governance landscape for a while (e.g. Van der Leun and Bouter 2015) – and through the lobbying work of NGOs at the start of the programme, this centralized idea of shelters as national holding spaces to return migrants became less prominent.

In the last five years, the state agencies have given away some of its coordinating powers to local bodies and non-state actors in the LVV programme. This does not make the state less powerful per se, as this distribution of roles was deliberately designed based on the idea that NGOs might work more effectively with to-be-returned migrants that find themselves in vulnerable positions. Again, the winning of trust of migrants seems to be the key issue at stake, which does raise questions regarding autonomy of migrants in return processes (Maâ 2023). At the same time, it is quite clear that a number of local actors and NGOs in the LVV programmes participated in these pilots with a rather different interpretation of what ‘sustainable solutions’ should be prioritized to combat irregularity in the Netherlands. With their persistent legal advocacy practices of NGOs, the spaces of contestation have been stretched in recent years. With the more authoritative approach of the newly installed government in 2024, and the discontinuation of the national financing of the programme, it remains to be seen how trust and partnerships will be re-negotiated through the interrelations we have outlined throughout this report.

⁸⁴ Prior to the Bed Bad Brood discussion in the Netherlands, the International Network of Local Initiatives with Asylum Seekers (INLIA) was involved in funding local shelter initiatives. Municipalities provided funding to the INLIA network and INLIA in return financed shelter initiatives (see Van der Leun and Boutler 2015). Today, the LVV in Groningen is provided by INLIA Groningen.

7. Conclusion

This report has provided both an overview of the return migration infrastructures (RMIs) in the Netherlands through the flowmap of Chapter 4 as well as more in-depth analyses of the daily practices and relations of these RMIs. Return migration governance in the Dutch context is difficult to understand from a harsh divide of voluntary return vs. forced removals. We rather start from the continuum of coercion, as put forward by Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou (2024). In most coercive setting – migrant detention – assisted return programmes are running, and in some cases trajectories that have started with NGOs offering return counselling end up in the administration as coerced returns. More importantly, pushing, imposing and incentivizing returns (ibid.) are all three inherent elements of the RMIs of the Netherlands, and these strategies are put forward by a variety of actors. In this regard, it is important to repeat that the Dutch authorities, in comparison with other European countries, are relatively ‘successful’ in its goal to return migrants that have no right to stay in the Netherlands (Leerkes and Van Houte 2020).

Just a quick glimpse of the flowmap in Chapter 4 already illustrates the multifold relations and interdependencies involved in the Dutch RMI. The flowmap also underlines that the particular design of a stringent post-arrival enforcement regime (Leerkes and Van Houte 2020) that includes a double role of DTenV regievoorders as case workers promoting both assisted returns as well as materializing forced returns, detention facilities, a continuum of administrative practices, still has multiple escape routes, loopholes and feedback loops in this landscape. To a large extent these escapes and feedback loops can be explained by the collective agency of migrants, communities, lawyers and advocacy groups contesting the return migration governance of the Dutch state. At times, the contestation comes more or less from the inside, as we have seen in the case of the LVVs where some organizations put priorities on regularization instead of returns. This contestation might not always be a deliberate act of resistance, but may also relate to a different organizational position or ‘scale’ one is working from. One respondent described the latter in telling ways from the LVV setting:

On a higher level, one is basically interested in the larger numbers, and they more or less think in binary ways *staying or leaving*. However, on the local level, you think, tjee, this is a complicated case. Regardless the way we do it, we should find a solution for it (NGO in LVV programme 1).

The de-centered position we put forward in this report does indeed move away from simplistic binary situations. This does not mean that straightforward and ‘smooth’ removal processes do not occur, as we have also addressed some of the ‘lopende band werk’ of DTenV workers. The contrasting realities do not only relate to inter-organizational frictions, but also to intra-organizational frictions (e.g. the charter flights that caused time pressure but did not work out, or the emphasis on datafication within DTenV).

It would be a misreading, however, to see the increasing complexity as a clear and pure sign of policy dysfunction and contestation only. There is a governance architecture (Van Riemsdijk et al 2021) behind this landscape that can be seen as a form of ‘ordered chaos’ by design (Koinova et al. 2024) that allows for informal practices to make the formal rules work (Borelli and Lindberg 2024). NGOs offering return and reintegration assistance are involved in the Dutch RMI *because* they do things differently and, in so doing they, complement the practices of state authorities (see also Kalir and Wissink 2016). They build trust and partnerships in the

countries of origin in a *different* way than the DTenV or the IOM, and that is why the Dutch authorities are interested in these services. This incorporation of NGOs offering return assistance does not only raise questions about the commercialization of migration governance, but also about accountability and transparency.

An issue that is less easy to visualize in this flowmap, is the shifting contexts and temporalities the RMI is embedded in. Country lists change, diplomatic relations may become warmer and colder, relations between NGOs and state actors may be filled with more or less tension over time, local city administrations change, funding opportunities for NGOs may rise and disappear, a new Minister of Immigration Affairs joined the scene stressing the power of coercion and importance of border control, the LVV programme is officially discontinued, etc. In other words, RMIs are shaped by a constantly shifting and multilevel (geo)political landscape, and this landscape is constantly navigated by all actors involved, from DTenV regiovoorders to migrants. For DTenV regiovoorders their relational work with external partners in the field and temporal gymnastics are increasingly important. For migrants, however, the crucial issue of who to trust becomes increasingly diffuse, especially when they would realize how some information shared with NGOs or trust persons in asylum accommodations may travel from one desk to the other.

Finally, one has to realize that many of the complexities involved have actually not been included in this report. In other, words, the analysis is to a large extent bound to a Dutch setting. It is important to stress that relations in the RMI travel well beyond the Dutch borders. This includes again diplomatic relations and ‘migration deals’ between states, formal and informal readmission agreements, but also partnerships between NGOs as well as a further Europeanization of return governance through the gradual involvement of Frontex. All these developments imply the incorporations of more and more actors (see Marino et al. 2023), raising new questions of power imbalances, finance, accountability and trust in a cross-border setting.

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Appendix 1: Overview of return statistics (Eurostat & DTeNV)

Data	Year	TCNs found to be illegally present	Asylum applications	TCNs refused entry at the border	Dublin returns	The categories included here are based on available Eurostat data						Related alternative national category of official (annual) data on return		
						TCNs ordered to leave		TCNs returned following an order to leave (annual)	TCNs returned following an order to leave, by type of return					
						Total ordered to leave	Return decisions issued for		assisted return	non-assisted	forced return	Independent	Independent without	Total
	2015	3150	44970	2295	n/a	19015	19015	8385	n/a	n/a	1850	3320	5070	10240
	2016	2760	20945	2700	n/a	25310	25310	11890	4640	6470	2220	6760	8100	17080
	2017	2120	18210	2410	n/a	20750	20750	8195	1530	2810	3390	3400	10170	16960
	2018	2790	24025	2555	1850	17935	17935	8830	2150	3480	2650	3610	8620	14880
	2019	3565	25200	2900	2420	25435	25435	11055	3040	n/a	2760	4460	9660	16880
	2020	3640	15255	1980	1280	21100	21100	8715	2550	n/a	1650	2630	6880	11160
	2021	5010	26525	3745	850	17300	17300	2540	2233	n/a	1630	2100	5600	12090
	2022	5510	37025	3070	970	15740	15740	975	2478	n/a	1850	2450	4310	8610
		Eurostat	Eurostat	Eurostat	DT&V ⁸⁶	Eurostat	Eurostat	Eurostat	EMN for 2016/	EMN Factsheet	DT&V	DT&V	DT&V	

Table 1: Data on third country nationals, irregularity, asylum, refused entries (Source: Ebrahim and Strik 2024, Annex 1.1)

⁸⁵ Years 2015, 2016 and 2017 are retrieved from EMN reports that build on the DT&V statistics while 2018-2022 are retrieved directly from the DT&V. There are inconsistencies in the EMN reports concerning the naming of this category of returns. In 2016 it is named “voluntary departure” in 2017 “independent return” and in 2018 “assisted voluntary departure”.

⁸⁶ Ministerie van Justitie en Veiligheid, “Instroom- en vertrekcijfers,” Over DTenV, *Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek*, <https://www.dienstterugkeerenvertrek.nl/over-dtv/cijfers>, accessed on 1-8-2024.

Appendix 2: The flowmap enlarged

Actors: red = state authorities, purple = NGOs and the IOM offering return assistance, yellow = the national refugee council (VWN), shelter organisations and migrant support groups, grey = local government, dark yellow = EU return programmes, green = lawyers, blue = other actors. **Coordination platforms:** squares in light grey. **Processual outflow of migrants (where migrants go or are sent to next)** (dotted lines). The dark grey flag-like shapes indicate the outcome of the processes involved.

Appendix 3: DTenV's Visualization of Return Migration Governance

Source: DTenV website, [Printversie infographic terugkeerproces](#) | [Publicatie](#) | [Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek](#), accessed on 19-9-2024

Appendix 4: Visualizing the LVV Programmes

1. Route asylum seekers as presented in the Dutch media based on the first LVV plans in April 2015: [Even wat bed-bad-en-broodnodige uitleg \(nos.nl\)](https://www.nos.nl), accessed on 19-9-2024. The question of “Wil je meewerken aan vertrek?” (do you like to cooperate on your return?) underlines the built-in conditionality of this programme.

Steps in the LVV

2. Routes in LVV programme of Amsterdam, Source RGOA (2022)

Appendix 5. Visualizing the sharing of medical data

Explanation: this flow chart shows the main question that allows (or not) the sharing of medical information in case of an asylum procedure (with forced removal in the red and orange textboxes). Without translating, it becomes already clear that it concerns a wide range of actors as well as boundaries. It is worth noting that the text accompanying this chart underlines that these are only the ‘usual cases’ and that the incorporation of exceptions would make the chart unreadable.⁸⁷

Schema 2: Overdrachtsmomenten medische informatie bij asielpprocedure (schema op hoofdlijnen)

⁸⁷ [Handreiking uitwisseling medische informatie in de vreemdelingenketen | Richtlijn | Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek](#), accessed on 9-1-2025

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